

standICT.eu 2026

ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

FOLLOWING THE FELLOWS

**IMPACT REPORT FROM
FUNDED APPLICANTS TO
THE STANDICT.EU 2026
FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME**

NINTH OPEN CALL

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Disclaimer

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About StandICT.eu

The project is coordinated by [Trust-IT Srl](#) (IT) acting as a technical coordinator, and [Dublin City University](#) (IE) acting as financial coordinator, supported by its partners [AUSTRALO](#) (ES), [European Digital SME Alliance](#) (BE), [Fraunhofer](#) (DE) and [Open Forum Europe](#) (BE).

Acknowledgements

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Finally, we would like to thank all our **EUOS Technical Working Groups** (European Observatory for ICT Standardisation) **chairs** and **members** for their investment in gathering expertise and producing outstanding landscape reports of the standardisation status across different ICT sectors.

■ Foreword

The European Green Deal & the New Industrial Strategy for Europe call for a strong EU presence in international Standardisation development. The recent significant shifts in the geopolitical environment call for increasing the intensity of the EU presence in international standardisation committees. Building up a strong and sustainable pool of European Standardisation competent professionals who are ready to engage in European and International Standardisation is crucial. With this we are pleased to contribute to this already engaged community through the “Following the Fellows” series Impact Reports, now in its 8th edition under the new StandICT.eu 2026 project, continuing the work of the precursor edition, proving a tangible testimony of the impact generated by European ICT experts working in collaboration with international Standardisation Developing Organisations (SDOs), thanks to the financial support provided through the StandICT.eu 2026 Fellowship Programme, as a paramount part of the broader mission of the StandICT.eu 2026 Coordination and Support Action.

The main purpose of these regular publications is to display the work carried out by our fellows and illustrate the demonstrable outcomes that excellent research can bring to both society and the economy (SMEs or industry at large). Therefore, we substantiate how each effort in which the fellows are engaged provides a potential benefit to society and contributes to achieving specific, desired societal outcomes because of the ICT Standardisation efforts.

As we move forward, our commitment to bolstering the EU’s role in international standardisation remains strong. The “Following the Fellows” series is not only a testament to the achievements of our fellows but also serves as an inspiration and a call to action for future standardisation professionals. By highlighting the critical work of these individuals, we aim to underscore the importance of ICT standardisation in driving innovation, ensuring competitive advantages, and contributing to the sustainability and resilience of society and the economy at large.

We invite the standardisation community, policymakers, industry stakeholders, and all interested parties to engage with the insights and findings presented in these reports.

Maria Giuffrida

StandICT.eu 2026 Project Coordinator,
Trust-IT Services Srl

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■ Introduction

This report details the outcomes of the final cohort of fellows supported by the StandICT.eu 2026 Programme. It shares perspectives and the first results of the fellowships that were financed by the 9th open call¹.

Our team is delighted to showcase this series of StandICT.eu 2026 fellowship stories, which feature the funded experts detailing the addressed standards and ICT landscapes, and how these will fill the identified gaps and impact the related stakeholders and society. The results obtained by our fellows fully respond to many of the objectives set out in the EU Strategy on Standardisation. They mainly prioritise and address standardisation needs in strategic ICT areas, enhance European leadership in global standards, support innovation and improve the overall integrity of the European standardisation system.

Standards are at the core of the EU Single Market and global competitiveness, and play a fundamental (if sometimes invisible) role in our daily lives. They can ensure the interoperability of products and services, reduce costs, improve safety, and foster innovation.

At the same time, standards act as powerful drivers for innovation and growth by helping researchers bring their innovations to market and disseminate technological advances, as standards make their results transparent and ensure high quality. One of the critical purposes of StandICT.eu 2026 is to support the activity of European ICT experts to contribute to the modernisation and consolidation of the European standardisation system as well as to the valorisation of their research outputs, to efficiently respond to the EU's ambitions towards different thematic ICT areas, such as Metaverse and Digital Product Passport, which were the focus of the announcement of the 9th Open Call.

The primary purpose of this document is to share the results attained through the work carried out by the 42 funded experts and to showcase the most relevant outcomes, creating awareness of the potential impact and repercussions of such effects on commerce, industry, governmental policies and strategies and society. Each StandICT.eu2026 funding batch has a dedicated impact report, demonstrating the key findings, contributions, and observations made with the StandICT.eu community, the European Commission, the Multi-Stakeholder Platform for ICT Standardisation, the SDOs, and other interested parties, including all actors within our ever-growing StandICT.eu community.

In this funding batch, **in total, 42 fellowships** were granted, tackling the five policy areas as defined in the ICT Standardisation Rolling Plan 2025²:

- ▶ **Foundational drivers: 7 fellowships** focusing on Cybersecurity (5 fellowships), and E-Privacy (2).
- ▶ **Key enablers and security: 18 fellowships** focusing on Artificial Intelligence (6 fellowships), 5G/6G (3), Accessibility of ICT (1), Data interoperability (2), Electronic identification (2), Internet of Things (2), and Quantum technologies (2).
- ▶ **Innovation for Digital Single Market: 7 fellowships** focusing on Blockchain and DLT (3 fellowships), Web 4.0 and virtual worlds (2), E-Invoicing (1), and FinTech & RegTech Standardisation (1).
- ▶ **Sustainable growth: 8 fellowships** focusing on Circular Economy including Digital Product Passport (3), Digitisation of European Industry (1), Robotics and autonomous systems (1), Smart and sustainable cities (2), and Smart Grids and Smart Metering (1).

1 <https://www.standict.eu/index.php/standicteu-2026-9th-open-call>

2 <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/rolling-plan-2025>

Overview of the Open Call #9

This open call was running from May 28th until June 27th, 2025. It received a record number of 120 applications, of which 42 were selected for funding, with an overall 313 391€ granted. This batch marks the final round of [StandICT.eu](https://standict.eu) 2026 Fellowship programme that has supported overall 342 fellowships.

The StandICT.eu Open Calls target European ICT standardisation experts who contribute to international SDOs, work groups, and/or technical committees on any of the priority topics outlined in the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation. Due to their current strategic importance at the EU level, applications focusing on the issues of Virtual Worlds and Digital Product Passport are highly encouraged. However, this open call was open for applications tackling a broad range of ICT domains (as encompassed in the ICT Rolling Plan for Standardisation) and treated equally.

Fellowship Profiles

The funded applications encompass a broad geographic spectrum, spanning 17 different EU or associated countries, with the majority of experts hailing from Spain, the United Kingdom, and Germany. 21% of the funded experts are female, reflecting the broader context of ICT and standardisation professionals, where the majority of workers are male. Moreover, 21% of the financed fellows are new to the StandICT.eu programme, and the remainder are returning fellows who have already benefited from a funded StandICT.eu fellowship.

The retained fellowships are represented by a balance across key technologies and a broad spectrum of SDOs that will benefit from the applicants' competence and expertise. As outlined in the figure below, a large portion of the granted fellows have chosen their focus across various horizontal and vertical ICT areas; the most popular places in this batch include artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and Web 4.0 and virtual worlds. Moreover, this funding batch is marked by various vertical ICT areas the fellowships cover, namely FinTech & RegTech Standardisation as well as Smart and sustainable cities.

Figure 1 - Overview of the #9 Open Call key results and insights

Engaged SDOs, Organisations and European Projects

62% of the fellows' activity contributes to the activities of Committees or Working Groups operating in global SDOs, including ISO/IEC, ISO ITU, IEEE, and IETF, ISO while the remainder works with European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), covering CEN, CEN/CENELEC and ETSI, or with international standardisation associations, including OASIS.

Finally, 14 European or nationally funded and innovation research projects (see Table 1) are related to the engaged work in the OC#9 fellowships, focusing on different horizontal and vertical technologies.

Project name	ICT Area	Funding Programme	Related StandICT.eu Fellows
EURINV – Implementing the European Standard in consolidated eInvoicing cloud platforms		Connecting Europe Facility	Svante Schubert
PHOENi2X	Cybersecurity	HorizonEurope	Mateusz Zych
SYNAPSE			
XTRUST-6G	6G		
Qu-Test	Quantum technologies	HorizonEurope	Witold Jacak
BIOCODES	Artificial intelligence, data	HorizonEurope	Kira C. Lemke
NoLeFa	Artificial intelligence	HorizonEurope	Lauriane Aufrant
TEF-Health	eHealth	Digital Europe	João Manuel Leitão Quintas
EU4MEDTECH		HorizonEurope	
DTRIP4H		HorizonEurope	
SENSE	Virtual worlds	Digital Europe	Antonio Jara
TransIT	Digital Twins	the UKRI Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) (UK)	Paul Harvey
QUICOPTSAT	5G and beyond, 6G	European Space Agency (ESA)	Godred Fairhurst

Now, we are delighted to share with you the insights from our latest granted fellows' work – and we genuinely hope that these results encourage you to get involved in our StandICT.eu community and join our Fellowship Programme under our forthcoming Open Calls, the European Observatory for ICT Standards (EUOS) - via the Technical Working Groups (TWGs) delivering up-to-date landscape and gap analysis, and finally Standards Academy training future experts in ICT Standardisation.

Together, we shape and reinforce the European and international ICT standardisation arena!

1.

Foundational drivers

Travel Support as a Session Chair for ETSI Security Conference 2025

Alex Cadzow

Senior Cybersecurity and Human Factors Researcher, Cadzow Communications Consulting Ltd.

United Kingdom

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ETSI Technical Committee Cyber

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship supported my contribution to the ETSI Security Conference 2025, where I chaired a session entitled, “Digital Sovereignty and Societal Impact, Are We in the age of the Splinternet?” explored the risk of the creation of the Splinternet and how different groups use online services and networks provide challenges for one-size-fits-all security approaches. It explored how this impacts security, privacy and safety. From a European perspective, this topic is important to discuss as regulations like GDPR and the AI Act have created a different environment for companies to comply with and offer great protections to consumers compared to places with more lax regulations. Also, as the landscape of the internet has become divided around regional lines, e.g, the Chinese Internet, Russian Internet, European Internet, it has led to different expectations and norms around how the internet is used and accessed. Understanding this is vital if the Internet is to continue to be a place where ideas and knowledge are freely shared (as in the original dream) and the impact this is having on the spread of misinformation, deep fakes and other online threats, which are impacting how we interact and use the internet today. By discussing these topics, we can begin to tackle and talk about potential methods to mitigate against the harms of the splinternet.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The activity of this call as Chair for the ETSI Security Conference Session, Digital Sovereignty and Societal Impact, are we in the age of the Splinternet? will only have a minimal impact on European interests standards landscape. This topic aims to have an open discussion about the issues surrounding digital sovereignty and social impact. It had presentations discussing different viewpoints on this from major companies and standards organisations on how they approach these topics. With major EU legislation and regulations like GDPR, AI Act, DSA, DMA creating a different environment that companies must comply it is an important area to understand, regardless of the positive aspects (for example improved data protection for consumers) or the negative challenges faced (for example increased cost to prove conformity by certification).

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

Due to the one-shot type of this fellowship, there were limited achieved contributions. These included successful attendance and Chairing of the session Digital Sovereignty and Societal Impact, are we in the age of the Splinternet?

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

No since this was a one-shot fellowship supporting my participation to ETSI Security Conference 2025.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

This topic and session was designed to provoke thought and discussion and it achieved those goals, which were nicely achieved.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.etsi.org/events/2481-etsi-security-conference-oct2025

CACAO v3.0: Enhancing Interoperable Cybersecurity Playbooks for EU-wide Response

Mateusz Zych

Cybersecurity Research Scientist, University of Oslo
Norway

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

OASIS Collaborative Automated Course of Action Operations (CACAO)
TC

Role

Secretary of CACAO TC

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The fellowship addressed key limitations found in version 2.0 of the OASIS Collaborative Automated Course of Action Operations (CACAO) standard. While CACAO v2.0 introduced the first machine-readable format for cybersecurity playbooks, real-world use revealed gaps that limited interoperability and automation. The most critical issues included ambiguous schema elements, unclear execution semantics, and limited support for graphical and modular representations needed to visualize and exchange playbooks. From a European standpoint, these shortcomings directly affected operations. SOCs, CSIRTs, and critical infrastructure operators faced difficulties creating executable playbooks, hindering the coordinated responses envisioned by the NIS2 Directive, the Cyber Solidarity Act, and the EU Cyber Crisis Blueprint.

The fellowship, therefore, focused on three main goals:

1. Consolidating feedback from European and international stakeholders who implemented CACAO v2.0.
2. Designing and drafting CACAO v3.0 — a major revision introducing structural schema improvements, more precise execution semantics, and modular extensibility.
3. Aligning the work with EU cybersecurity policy and operational priorities so that standardized, machine-readable playbooks can support coordinated preparedness and response.

The effort resulted in the ongoing working CACAO v3.0 Draft Specification and accompanying validation outputs, now progressing toward formal adoption within OASIS. By resolving the main technical and semantic issues, the fellowship strengthened Europe's role in cybersecurity standardization. It established a solid, vendor-neutral foundation for automated, collaborative cyber defense across the EU.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Within the ICT standards landscape, the results strengthen Europe's capacity to coordinate and automate cross-border cyber defense actions. CACAO v3.0 provides a technical backbone

for implementing the goals of the NIS2 Directive, the Cyber Solidarity Act, and the EU Cyber Crisis Blueprint, enabling standardized, machine-readable procedures for preparedness, detection, response, and recovery. It also supports ENISA and CyCLONe priorities by improving interoperability between SOCs, CSIRTs, and national authorities.

The fellowship further enhanced interoperability with related standards and initiatives, including:

- ▶ STIX/TAXII, ensuring CACAO playbooks can interface with cyber-threat-intelligence workflows.
- ▶ TAC Ontology, providing a semantic bridge between contextual threat data and operational actions.
- ▶ Broader frameworks in ETSI TC CYBER, CEN/CENELEC JTC 13, and ITU-T SG17, where security automation and incident-response alignment are ongoing topics.

By delivering the CACAO v3.0 Draft Specification and validation examples, the fellowship made tangible progress toward a unified, vendor-neutral framework for cybersecurity automation, positioning Europe as a key driving force in international standardization.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Yes. The development of CACAO v3.0 directly benefits European SMEs by reducing technical and financial barriers to adopting advanced cybersecurity practices. The standard's open and vendor-neutral design allows smaller organizations to integrate automated playbooks into their operations without relying on costly, proprietary tools. This strengthens their incident response capabilities and helps them meet the security and reporting obligations set out in the NIS2 Directive and the Cyber Solidarity Act.

Beyond SMEs, CACAO v3.0 enhances resilience across European digital infrastructure by enabling harmonized, machine-readable playbooks that support faster, coordinated responses to incidents affecting critical services such as energy, healthcare, and public administration.

Impact on Society

The fellowship directly supports Europe's goals for cyber resilience, digital sovereignty, and trust in critical infrastructure. By improving CACAO's technical maturity and usability, the work enables more organizations—especially SMEs and public-sector entities—to adopt standardized, automated cybersecurity playbooks without reliance on proprietary technologies.

The resulting CACAO v3.0, with better schematics and semantics specification, offers easier, more coordinated responses to cyber incidents, reducing disruption to essential services such as healthcare, energy, and transport. It also reinforces cross-border cooperation and preparedness through machine-readable, reusable response procedures, enabling Member States and operators of essential services to collaborate under shared frameworks like NIS2 and the Cyber Solidarity Act.

Ultimately, this work enhances Europe's capacity to defend against complex threats while fostering open collaboration, transparency, and interoperability—key enablers of a secure and digitally independent European society

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

The fellowship directly supported the revision of an existing international standard — the OASIS Collaborative Automated Course of Action Operations (CACAO) specification. The work led to the development of CACAO version 3.0, a major update that introduces structural schema improvements, refined execution semantics, and modular extensibility mechanisms. These revisions address operational limitations identified in version 2.0 and align the standard with the above mentioned European cybersecurity frameworks.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The publication of CACAO version 3.0 has been delayed due to the standardization process, which requires extended review and consensus within the OASIS Technical Committee. The fellowship successfully produced the CACAO v3.0 suggestions and improvements, which introduced significant structural and semantic improvements to the newest specification draft. However, progressing this draft toward Committee Specification Draft (CSD) and eventual Public Review requires alignment among multiple international stakeholders. This is a normal and expected stage in the lifecycle of major OASIS standards, ensuring high technical quality and broad adoption. The updated timeline anticipates formal submission to public review in early 2026.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.oasis-open.org/committees/cacao

Cybersecurity for AI Systems in Standardisation under the EU AI Act for a secure digital fundament

Annegrit Seyerlein-Klug

Freelancer, asekcon Cybersecurity Consulting ICT and AI Germany

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 Artificial Intelligence WG5 for Cybersecurity for AI Systems

Role

Convener of the CEN CENELEC JTC21 WG5 for Cybersecurity for AI Systems

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The AI Act regulates the use of AI systems as standalone products and harmonized European standards (hENs) shall be the base for conformity with the AI Act. One of the related Standardization Request (SR) is a harmonized standard for Cybersecurity Specifications for AI Systems, which is not existing in Europe or international.

This fellowship supports me as convener of CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 WG 5 “Cybersecurity for AI Systems”, where I lead the development of this horizontal standard as a cornerstone of the AI Act’s implementation. It aims to define technical and organizational cybersecurity requirements that enable providers and deployers of high-risk AI systems to demonstrate compliance—via self- assessment or third-party evaluation—as a prerequisite for EU market access.

The challenge is the development of a mature standard by meeting the requirements of the AI Act and the requested timeline, which is still very short.

My role as convener was the planning, coordination and leading the WG for that as efficient as possible. We implemented some Ad Hoc Groups for specific items to work more in parallel. I also worked as expert for e.g. risk or quality management to support and accelerate the work over the summer.

Another challenge was the identification and coordination of the interplay with the other SR’s and Working Groups of the AI Act like risk-, quality management or robustness but also with the related EU regulation like Cyber Resilience Act. In that case, we created a Technical Coherence Group to meet between WGs e.g. for discussion and coordination content e.g. for risk.

I also participating CEN/CENELEC JTC 13 WG for Standards for CRA and exchanged with this group about riskmanagement and specific conventional cybersecurity for products to ensure coherence as much as possible.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship supports my contributions to the Standardization Request for the AI Act, especially to the request for Art.15 Cybersecurity. The name is "Cybersecurity Specifications for AI systems". Our project number JT021029 got now a EN number: prEN 18282 for the next step, which is public enquiry.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

European SMEs , which are providing risk or high risk AI systems in the European market are effected by the AI Act and in that case also from the standard I work for and contribute: Cybersecurity Specifications for AI- Systems.

Impact on Society

The AI Act has the goal to avoid or mitigate negative impact on people and society regarding Fundamental Rights, Health and Safety. All harmonized standards for the AI Act support this goal and request of the AI Act including the standard for Cybersecurity specifications for AI Systems.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am involved in the developpement a new harmonized standard for Cybersecurity Specifications for AI systems based on a the standardization request of the European commission

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

A standard has different stages to achieve. The inbetween goal and milestone of my convenorship and the WG was to bring the Working Draft (WD) in a such a mature form that it can be submitted for enquiry to all European National Bodies for official comments. We worked hard and achieved this milestone. The WD was submitted to the European Commission for review and to CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 to send to CCMC/ National Bodies. We also closed the discussion for the moment on some interplay parts. The next step will be the collection of comments and art with the comment resolution for the final version in some month. The publication of the standard is planned for mid of 2026.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://jtc21.eu/working-groups/>

Improving presentation and quality of Terminology for EN-ISO/IEC 15408 series and EN-ISO/IEC 18045

Elzbieta Andrukiewicz

*National Institute of Telecommunications, ITSEF Manager,
National Institute of Telecommunications
Poland*

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27/WG3 “Security evaluation, testing and specifications”

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship supports my participation to the revisions of ISO/IEC 15408 (multipart) and ISO/IEC 18045 editions finally published in 2022, considered several aspects of unification, synchronization, and consistency. One of them was terminology. It was decided that Part 1 would collect all terms from various parts. In that way terms and their definitions were reviewed, redundancies removed, different definitions of the same terms unified, and the quality of terminology was improved.

However, during the last stage (FDIS), based on the comment from ISO Editor, editors decided to identify the owners of terms and re-distribute terms among relevant parts.

The adverse impact on consistency of terminology used in the standards has been identified almost immediately, during current revision process. After final cross-checking before issuing the FDIS versions separate comments on terminology were collected for relevant parts, and they were handled in diverse ways by their editors.

A missing part dedicated exclusively to Vocabulary would allow avoiding inconsistencies in the terminology resulted in downgrading its quality. Additional benefit is that tedious, continual work towards removing inconsistencies and re-synchronizing terminology during every subsequent edition would not be necessary.

As ISO/IEC 15408 (multipart) and ISO/IEC 18045 are reference standard to several cybersecurity certification schemes including EUCC, this work is of the utmost priority when next revision of the standards is considered.

The biggest challenge is to add a new part to the 5-part standard in the way it would not disturb their implementations but quite contrary, facilitate the use of them once sixth part is published.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Starting from February 27, 2025, the first European Cybersecurity Certification scheme (EUCC) is in its operational phase. According to Commission Implementation Regulation

2024/482, art. 3(1) reference standards for EUCC are the following:

“The following standards shall apply to evaluations performed under the EUCC scheme:

- (a) the Common Criteria;
- (b) the Common Evaluation Methodology.”

Note that these standards are equivalent to EN-ISO/IEC 15408 series and EN-ISO/IEC 18045, respectively (see art. 2 of CIR 2024/482): Any subsequent versions of the standard will have direct impact on cybersecurity evaluations performed under the EUCC program.

ISO/IEC 15408-1:2022 Evaluation Criteria for IT security - Part 1: Introduction and general model.

ISO/IEC 15408-2:2022 Evaluation Criteria for IT security - Part 2: Security functional components

ISO/IEC 15408-3:2022 Evaluation Criteria for IT security - Part 3: Security assurance components

ISO/IEC 15408-4:2022 Evaluation Criteria for IT security - Part 4: Framework for the specification of evaluation methods and activities

ISO/IEC 15408-5:2022 Evaluation Criteria for IT security - Part 5: Pre-defined packages of security requirements

ISO/IEC 18045:2022 Evaluation criteria for IT security - Methodology for IT security evaluation

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society) Impact on Society

Gaining the customer confidence they are using secure and safe ICT products is the objective of security assessment. Considering technical complexity of cybersecurity evaluation these processes should rely on robust and mature standards. The customers and risk owners do not need to know all details of such evaluation, but they should have solid ground of trust in the results of evaluations usually expressed by the certificates.

Common Criteria provide highly sophisticated tools for gaining confidence in correct and sufficient implementations of security controls under the principles of the “cybersecurity-by-design-and-default” in the ICT products and the ground of their resilience in case of cyberattacks which could happen in the future.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. The current revision of ISO/IEC 15408 (multipart) and ISO/IEC 18045 is at the final (FDIS) Stage. One expects the publication at the beginning of 2026. However, facing many identified issues where the consolidation of terminology is only one of several to be solved early revision of the standards is likely to happen. For that reason, completing the analysis of vocabulary consolidation is essential to start the revision with new, sixth part of ISO/IEC 15408.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The new PWI was established and based on this a call of contribution was issued asking experts for contributions to the topic with the deadline to end of January 2026. Based on contributions the results of analysis will be presented at the SC27/WG3 meeting planned for March 2026. Considering it as possible reference material for a new part of ISO/IEC 15408 once a new revision of the standards is agreed.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/45306.html

Global blockchain and DLT standards on Security, Privacy and Identity

Julien Bringer

CEO, Kallistech

France

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection JWG 4
CEN/CENELEC JTC 19 (expert)
Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies

Role

Convener of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 JWG 4

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The development of internationally-recognized blockchain and DLT standards is the core goal of ISO/TC 307, as being the ISO framework for transversal standards. Even if Europe is very active with dedicated EU initiatives, given the global deployment and impact of these technologies, TC307 is expected to be the global venue for leading such standards. It is thus of great importance to ensure EU is actively represented in this committee and that liaisons with other ISO or CEN/CENELEC groups in which EU experts are already active are efficiently leveraged. Therefore, my fellowship targeted security, privacy and identity topics in the context of global standard governance.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The standards of interest covers in particular cybersecurity requirements and assurance of blockchain/DLT systems, for instance applied to smart contracts and blockchain systems, decentralised identity management, and enhanced privacy protection (with potential applications to privacy-sensitive domains). A good collaboration is in place between TC307 and SC27 within JWG4. Several Technical Reports have been published since 2020 and the group is now working on 7 projects for future international standards (privacy-related ISO/WD 24946 and ISO/WD 24876, security-related ISO/WD 25126, and the series of 3 parts of ISO/WD 24875 for smart contracts, and ISO/WD 23042 on decentralized identity, with the 3 first ones which might be published late 2026/early 2027 - thus the importance to actively support them), with latest projects on security of smart contracts (several parts) that have been accepted for development in August. There is also possibly a new project upcoming on cybersecurity information sharing (via the liaison with BGIN) and new requests expected from the participating countries to add further projects on digital identity to support further global interoperability on digital ID with decentralized technologies.

Given their potential impact, and also the EU activities on CRA and digital identity, it is thus important to support those activities, and additionally to link with the EU ecosystem.

The activity helps to ensure consistency and usefulness of blockchain/DLT standards within

a broader framework. It also supports the EU leadership roles on those organization and consistency with EU security, identity and privacy frameworks.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Blockchain and Distributed Ledger technologies are developed directly in a global environment and thus the activity impacts EU and SMEs in EU, as for the way EU specificities and regulations (e.g. GDPR, eIDAS, NIS, MiCA) considered as early as possible. Also many SMEs in EU are positioned around security of web 3.0 applications and on decentralized identity and future standards on this matter would be key for procurement.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. This fellowship supported my role as a convener, and within my WG, three new standardisation projects were accepted in August 2025 for smart contracts security:

- ▶ ISO/AWI 24875-1 Smart contract security — Part 1: Secure development
- ▶ ISO/AWI 24875-2 Smart contract security — Part 2: Code review
- ▶ ISO/AWI TS 24875-3 Smart contract security — Part 3: Holistic diagnostic method).

And a new project for cybersecurity information sharing is being proposed.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

There are different stages of maturity for the different projects., going from DIS, to CD and become Working Draft stage. Given the increasing number of projects (and more probably to come) it is recommended to ensure more EU experts can contribute.

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.iso.org/committee/6266604.html

www.iso.org/committee/45306.html

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/ords/f?p=205:7::::FSP_ORG_ID:2702172&cs=1800DC97241B3E480F4447B96339D2A58

Strategic Business Plan: ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 44 Consumer Protection in the Field of Privacy by Design

Jan Schallaböck

Partner, iRights.Law RAe
Germany

Sector

E-Privacy

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 44 – Consumer protection in the field of privacy by design, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27

Role

Chair of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 44 – Consumer protection in the field of privacy by design

Convener support officer at ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 5 – Identity management and privacy technologies

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship targets consumer-centric privacy by design in international standards work. Moreover, the Specific priorities, gaps and challenges identified are:

- ▶ Consumer trust and privacy gaps: Fragmented practice and fast-moving online services erode user trust; legal principles (e.g., privacy by design, accountability) are not consistently translated into usable, testable requirements.
- ▶ Stakeholder involvement: Consumer organisations and SMEs face high barriers to engage in lengthy, technical processes; national mirrors vary widely in how consumer voices are integrated.
- ▶ Skills & usability deficits: Lack of shared patterns (consent, transparency UX, data control) and uneven digital skills hinder meaningful participation and compliant implementations.
- ▶ Landscape fragmentation: Overlapping activities across SDOs make it hard for newcomers to find entry points, slowing delivery on e-privacy, safety, and transparency outcomes.

How the fellowship addressed these

This fellowship supports my engagement as the chair of Chair of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 44. The group's Strategic Business Plan (SBP) aims to respond to the challenges identified above in the following manners:

- ▶ The TC establishes an inclusive, modular work approach that supplements ISO 31700-1 with smaller, technology-/sector-specific deliverables—lowering thresholds for participation and speeding time-to-impact on safety, transparency, and e-privacy.
- ▶ Low-threshold stakeholder mechanisms: Communications/outreach plan and light-touch consultation formats to systematically bring in consumer groups and civil society, aligned with ISO/COPOLCO and relevant liaisons.
- ▶ SME: A stepwise, outcome-oriented approach envisaged in the SBP to accommodate different maturity levels and resource constraints, easing adoption by SMEs.

- ▶ Early scoping of verticals: Following the September 2025 SC 44 meetings in Kunming, first preliminary work is being initiated with additional verticals to follow.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This funded fellowship advanced the ICT Standards by establishing a dedicated global forum for consumer-centric privacy by design under ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 44

The specific standards-families addressed include:

- ▶ ISO 31700 Part 1: Consumer protection – Privacy by design for consumer goods and services - Part 1: High-level requirements (published Jan 2023)
- ▶ ISO 31700 Part 2: covering illustrative use-cases and implementation guidance
- ▶ ISO 31700 Part 3: preliminary work item (PWI) dealing with conformance, certification or vertical-sector applications (as foreseen in the Strategic Business Plan for SC 44)
- ▶ Complementary standards in SC 27/WG 5 on identity management & privacy technologies (e.g., de-identification frameworks, age-assurance systems)

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

European stakeholders—including consumer protection agencies, privacy NGOs, and SMEs—benefit from standards that operationalise the GDPR's intentions while ensuring international interoperability. Yet their effective participation requires active facilitation, particularly in new structures such as SC 44, which currently lack established consumer consultation mechanisms.

The fellowship addressed this through structured moderation, bilateral liaison efforts (e.g. SC 27, SC 37, SC 42, OECD, TACD), and the development of participation tools that lower the threshold for stakeholder input. In the long term, systematic integration of consumer needs into technical standardisation will create both societal and economic value—opening opportunities for European SMEs and civil-society actors to co-shape usable, rights-based privacy-by-design standards.

Impact on Society

The focused standards have several key societal impact:

- ▶ Consumer trust and transparency: By developing modular, user-centric privacy standards (ISO 31700 family), the work enables individuals to better understand, control, and contest how their personal data are used across digital services.
- ▶ Fairness and due process: Standardising transparency and accountability mechanisms strengthens procedural safeguards for consumers and ensures consistent respect for rights across jurisdictions.
- ▶ Inclusion and accessibility: SC 44's stakeholder model - outlined in the Strategic Business Plan - lowers participation barriers for consumer groups, NGOs, and SMEs, thus widening representation in global ICT standardisation.
- ▶ Digital skills and awareness: Reusable guidance and patterns developed under SC 44 support capacity-building for both implementers and end-users, contributing to digital-skills and literacy objectives in the EU.
- ▶ Socio-economic resilience: By reducing compliance costs and promoting interoperable privacy solutions, the standards ecosystem strengthens the competitiveness of European SMEs while reinforcing consumer rights and social trust online.

In sum, the fellowship advances a human-centred digital transformation, where privacy, transparency, and usability become intrinsic features of technology design—helping to operationalise European values of trust, accountability, and fairness in the global digital economy.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. As listed above, I support several new preliminary new work items have been initiated in SC 44, with more underway.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Important prerequisites for consumer engagement in standardisation have been established through the fellowship - most notably the approved SC 44 Strategic Business Plan, which embeds structured participation mechanisms, modular work formats, and SME-oriented maturity models. Several outreach activities were carried out with consumer and civil-society organisations to raise awareness and invite collaboration. However, this work must continue. Sustained outreach, capacity-building, and low-threshold consultation formats will be essential to turn these initial structures into active, long-term involvement and meaningful influence on standardisation outcomes.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/10778243.html

 <https://jtc1info.org/sd-2-history/jtc1-subcommittees/s>

Security and Privacy Enhancements for IEEE 802.11

Mathy Vanhoef

*Assistant Professor, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
Belgium*

Sector

E-Privacy

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEEE 802.11 Working Group (Wireless LANs) TGmf

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship supported my work in updating to the IEEE 802.11 standard to prevent a recently discovered security weakness. This weakness is related to mesh networks, where, without extra defenses, an adversary could inject arbitrary packets into protected mesh networks. We designed a defense to mitigate this challenging gap. Unique about our created defense is that it is fully backward compatible, meaning each individual mesh client can independently enable this defense. As a proof-of-concept, we also implemented this defense in the Linux kernel to demonstrate practicality and confirm it prevents attacks.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This work directly addresses the E-Privacy and Cybersecurity priority, since it improves the security and privacy of IEEE 802.11 networks, i.e., Wi-Fi networks. Since Internet of Things devices and smart cities often make use of mesh networks, my contributions also aid the IoT and Smart Cities priority. The defense was also designed to cause practically no overhead and without requiring new hardware, meaning existing devices can keep being used, ensuring sustainability and avoiding e-waste. Summarized, there were concrete proposed updates to the IEEE 802.11, and several other discussions to aid other ongoing efforts and discussions on future improvements.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

During the fellowship, I have been in contact with LANCOM, a European company providing Wi-Fi equipment, on improving the security of their devices, inspired by our research and contributions to the IEEE 802.11 standards. This allows European SMEs to take a leadership position on ensuring security and privacy in IEEE 802.11 equipment and networks.

Impact on Society

Privacy and security are core human rights in our eyes, and our standardization improvements support this societal right. More broadly, these contributions help us as a European player to influence the IEEE 802.11 standard with these values. The security improvements are also created with sustainability in mind, as their overhead is designed to be minimal and practically negligible, and is designed to be backward compatible to reduce e-waste.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes; my project supported the revision of an existing standard, namely IEEE 802.11 (IEEE 802.11 WG, TGmf / P802.11REVmf).

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

There are still several areas where security and privacy in IEEE 802.11 wireless protocols can improve. For instance, I had discussions on secure multi-password support and aiding the transition to post-quantum cryptography. I plan to actively contribute to these aspects since they also closely align with my academic research.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.ieee802.org/11/Reports/tgm_update.htm

2. Key enablers and security

The background features a glowing blue fingerprint scan in the center-right, with binary code (0s and 1s) scattered around it. On the left, there are several concentric, glowing blue circular lines. The bottom-left corner shows a green circuit board pattern. The overall color palette is dominated by dark blue, light blue, and green, creating a high-tech, digital atmosphere.

AI-Native for Autonomous 5G and 6G Networks

Paul Harvey

*Lecturer in Autonomous Networked Systems, University of Glasgow
United Kingdom*

Sector

5G and Beyond (6G)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ITU-T SG13 / Q20 - Future networks and emerging network technologies
ITU-T Focus Group on AI-Native Networks

Role

Vice chair of ITU-T Focus Group on AI-Native Networks (FG-AINN)

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

In my fellowship i have been working to support the challenge of native integration of AI in the context of communication networks. While much success has been achieved in addressing network use cases with intelligent technologies, this has predominantly been applied in a case by case basis, with resulting outputs added to the networks in an ad-hoc way. Instead, AI-native networks are envisioned to accommodate the ubiquitous and native deployment of AI-based solutions in the network.

Through the work of the ITU-T Focus Group on AI-Native Networks, I contributed to the elaboration of use case, and associated requirements. I have also been supporting on the analysis of relevant key technologies that are required to realise the requirements derived from the use cases.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship supports my engagement with the ITU-T Focus Group on AI-Native Networks, where I serve as vice-chair. This pre-standardisation group is studying the gap, use cases, technical enablers, and proof of concepts required to understand what standardisation is required for AI-native networks.

The engagement has lead to output documents relating to the characteristics and vocabulary around AI-Native networks, as well as the ongoing build-a-thon activities that support informing the standards development process. These have been submitted to SG13 as new standards work items.

The fellowship has also supported the elaboration of a draft standard (Y.KM-AN) which has been put forwards to SG13 for consent. This standard describes the role of knowledge management in autonomous networks.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

AI-native networks are set to increase the amount of automated operation within our networks, making them more scalable and resilient and decreasing OPEX. From a consumer perspective, this will translate to more reliable service operation at a lower cost.

Impact on Society

Integration of AI in the management and operation of telecommunication networks, supports increased automation, reducing the operational expenditure and increasing the reliability of their operation. Together, this supports cheaper, more resilient, and high quality critical national infrastructure for society that relies on such networks for entertainment, maintain societal bonds, education, emergency support, and commerce. In this way, this work in-directly supports this by supporting standardisation that eases the integration of AI in networks.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I supported the submission of new standards work items within SG13.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Given the nascent stage of AI-Native Networks, combined with the integral role of AI in future 6G networks, further work is required to bring clarity to the topic via standardisation.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/ainn

■ HA-ITU-T SG13 October-2025

Alojz Hudobivnik

*Freelancer, AH.TS Alojz Hudobivnik s.p.
Slovenia*

Sector

5G and Beyond (6G)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

| ITU-T SG13 “Future networks and emerging network technologies”

Role

Convener

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship supports my work targeting IMT-2020 (5G) and beyond network aspects. This covers studies on the requirements and capabilities for networks based on the service scenarios of IMT-2020 and beyond. This study includes the development of recommendations on the framework and architecture design including also network-related aspects of reliability, quality of service (QoS) and security. Furthermore, it includes interworking with current networks including IMT-Advanced, etc. Standardization work continues with the integration of new technologies, new insights, and new requirements of different verticals. It is very important that EU science, industry, and also users are well represented and engaged in this process.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Since its creation, the JCA “IMT2020 and beyond” has been charged with maintenance and regular population and updating the IMT-2020 and beyond standards roadmap. This project proved to be important and instrumental for the telecommunication industry as it shows the full map of activities, technical domains, and achievements of ITU, different regional standard development organizations, fora, consortia, and associations operating in the IMT-2020 and beyond arena. Furthermore, it serves as a tool to identify the gaps in standardization where efforts should be applied in the nearest future.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Well-defined and globally standardized 5G ecosystem is important for operators and all suppliers of SW and HW components which gradually develops. Additionally, the EU Rolling Plan for ICT (2025) clearly defines the importance of 5G infrastructure for verticals and defines needed standardization actions.

Impact on Society

The European Commission’s Multi-Stakeholder Platform (MSP) on ICT standardisation has suggested that supportive measures be taken to enhance the involvement of EU-based experts in international standardization efforts, especially in new and innovative fields. Additionally, the platform recommends that standards organizations make information regarding ongoing and new development projects and work items readily accessible to the public. For standardisation activities pertaining to regulatory and policy matters, sufficient

background information and assumptions should be provided. To ensure the seamless flow of information, personal presence during daily operations of Standard Development Organizations (SDOs) is crucial. In my capacity, I was able to meet these expectations when working within the ITU-T SG13's work area.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

This activity resulted to finalised and approved revision 5 of Supplement 59 to ITU-T Y.3100-series "IMT-2020 and beyond standardisation roadmap" where I am the editor. Additionally, I contribute to the final content and final review of the development for two new Recommendations to be state of the art: ITU-T Y.DTN-DataFrame: " Digital Twin Network - Framework and functional requirements of data domain in network digital twin layer ", ITU-T Y.ICN-INP: "Information-centric networking in networks beyond IMT-2020: Requirements and capabilities of node to support in-network processing in networks beyond IMT-2020)";

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Participating in global standardization can be a costly endeavor, especially in the field of telecommunications where uniform global standards are necessary for globalisation. To achieve European initiatives, contributions, and goals, it is essential to have delegates and experts present in global Standard Development Organizations (SDOs) such as the ITU-T. However, despite the significance of the work carried out in SG13, there is a noticeable lack from EU expert's in-person attendance, typically representing just 2 or 3 out of 200 delegates.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/studygroups/2025-2028/13/Pages/default.aspx

Travel Support for the Montreal Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) plenary meeting

Godred Fairhurst

*Professor, University of Aberdeen
United Kingdom*

Sector

5G and Beyond (6G)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IETF Transport and Services Working Group (TSVWG)
IETF Congestion Control Working Group (ICC WG)
IETF QUIC Working Group (QUIC WG)
IETF SCONE Working Group (SCONE WG)
IETF Internet Engineering Steering Group (IESG)

Role

Chair of IETF Internet Engineering Steering Group (IESG)
Editor, reviewer and contributor in the other groups

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This one-shot fellowship supported my travel to the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) plenary meeting on November 2025 in Montreal, Canada. It supported actions as a contributor, reviewer and chair/area director of work related to Web and Internet transport. The funding supported on-going efforts to ensure next generation specifications published by the IETF are safe and operate reliably across a wide range of Internet infrastructure - from broadband access, to 5G to cable networks. I sought to promote the work and opportunities in the IETF by active participation in activities such as the “newcomers meetings” and other activities co-located with time IETF plenary meeting.

Participation also helped standardise recent research into new transport mechanisms in my contribution towards publication of draft-ietf-tsvwg-careful-resume as a proposed standard, and to ensure that draft-ietf-tsvwg-careful-resume-qlog completes, enabling it also to progress to finalisation as an RFC. I also personally contributed to complete draft-ietf-ccwg-ratelimited-increase for later publication as an RFC.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

As an IESG member, I review all new IETF standards from a perspective of robustness and resilience and how they address core IETF concerns around privacy and security. Overall engagement in the WIT area of the IETF can help ensure that the inevitable changes in the application traffic or network path do not impact a continued reliable and robust performance. This meeting provided opportunities to coordinate with people, and other organisations (including a 3GPP coordination meeting).

As a part of in-person attendance at the meeting, I will sought to encourage the participation of new contributors and to ensure the safety and robustness of the protocols being developed.

This is critical, because to build successful standards, requires experts to engage as working group chairs and people to provide detailed informed review of documents.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society) Impact on Society

The IETF is the principal Internet SDO. IETF standards and guidelines are important to Broadband Infrastructure, ensuring resilience and security of Internet data.

The standards published by the IETF define the software, protocols, and practices implemented by equipment vendors and operators. When adopted by industry, these standards will be deployed by international companies such as Apple, Google, Meta, Cloudflare and others. Specifications in the working groups for which I am the responsible Area Director include: Differentiated Services, new transport protocol mechanisms and the effects of pervasive encryption, protocol design, network infrastructure operation. It is important that new specifications consider user privacy, security, resilience and robustness to build the next generation of Internet applications and service.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contributed to a standard item “QUIC Encrypted Transport”.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Specifications in the area that I lead include transport-related protocols and best current practices, secure protocols and the effects of pervasive encryption, protocol design, network infrastructure operation and user privacy for new and proposed architectures (including work on protocols targeting 5G and Docsis).

Participation in document review is critical prior to publication, all documents receive detailed review, including review by the IESG, where I review as member and support the review by the TSV-ART review team. The finally published standards are foundational to the operation of the Internet, and pivotal to launching new products and creating the services to Internet users.

I have both received and contributed comments working with a wide variety of IETF participants via email, on-line, at WG meetings and in face-to-face discussions. In my role as a reviewer and chair, I help others develop code and help explore the results of experiments. I also participate to the IETF Hackathon, and other meetings. Such work needs to continue.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/wit/about/>

Using accessibility standards to increase the cybersecurity of the full range of consumers

Gill Whitney

*Independent Expert, Middlesex University
United Kingdom*

Sector

Accessibility of ICT products and services

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CLC/JTC 13/WG 9 “Special Working Group on the Cyber Resilience Act”
ETSI Cyber
ETSI Cyber CRA (CYBEREURS)

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This work builds on the work I carried out for my previous application (06-842 Enabling the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) standards to better support Vulnerable Consumers) by promoting the results of this work in both a conference presentation and an academic paper). These publications promoted how the combination of accessibility and cybersecurity standards could enable a wider variety of people to be kept safe and secure when using digital products. It therefore contributed to both the content of the standards being written for the Cyber Resilience Act (including a specific annex on ‘Accessible and Inclusive CyberSecurity’) and to the knowledge of the writers of those standards.

The group of people who would benefit from this element of this content and knowledge includes children, people with disabilities, novice users or users who cannot focus completely on the security of their connected devices. This category of people includes many who may be less wealthy and therefore may be using older or recycled devices.

My priority with the presentation and paper is to ensure that both the standard writers and the manufactures understand the importance of creating and maintaining products with digital elements so that they meet the need of all end users. Their responsibilities include following the relevant accessibility requirements of the procurement directive, web accessibility directive and European accessibility act.

The main challenge was the need to work with highly intelligent experts in the field of Cyber Security who fear that considering the needs of vulnerable, novice users could result in a reduction in the overall level of Cyber Security rather than supporting all people including those who are just having a ‘bad’ or distracted day.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship focused on the standards being created with respect to the Cyber Resilience Act CRA³ It included attending meetings of:

- ▶ CEN/CLC/JTC 13/WG 9 “Special Working Group on Cyber Resilience Act”

3 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R2847>

- ▷ CEN/CLC/JTC 13/WG 9 Project team One – working on the main horizontal standard, ‘Cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements — General principles for cyber resilience’ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=legisum:4797302>.
- ▷ ETSI Cyber Meetings (parts relevant for the work on the CRA)
- ▷ ETSI CYBER-EUSR Meetings (focusing on the vertical standards which refer to products which have a direct connection to the user).

I attended these meetings whilst working on the:

- ▷ ETSI presentation.
- ▷ The draft academic paper.
- ▷ The final version of the annex to the main horizontal standard, ‘Cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements — General principles for cyber resilience’ on ‘Accessible and Inclusive CyberSecurity’.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

My contribution impacts in SMEs in a small but important way. The requirements of consumers with respect to how security information (such as updates or warnings) needs to be presented to end users in a clear, easy to understand and timely manner, without the use of unnecessary, unfamiliar terminology. Many SMEs will have access to or employ Cyber Security experts. They will therefore have similar requirements for information to be presented in a clear, useable, timely and concise way. I have referred to the issue of information to be presented in a useable way in a number of meetings. This is particularly relevant with respect to information impacting purchasing decisions or with reference to security updates.

Impact on Society

My work supports ICT accessibility and digital skills. It did this by promoting the requirements of end users when these people were acting as part of a system involving the use of products with digital elements. These end users will include vulnerable end users. In these systems the end users will be involved in a range of set up and management activities with respect to the digital elements including choosing the products and their application, selecting and maintaining levels of Cybersecurity and making decisions on when the product has reached its end of life.

Products with digital elements include health monitoring and quality of life products which can improve the life and health of the end user, if they fail or become unsafe, they may impact the physical, sensory or cognitive health of the end user. If their operation becomes uncertain, they may cause stress, which impacts the cognitive health of the end user.

By supporting the end users to make sensible decisions when selecting or maintaining a product with digital elements, the followers of the relevant CRA standard will increase the digital skills of the end users. This can be achieved by enabling standards writers to create standards which consider the needs of all end users. The aim of this project was to assist the standard writers to do this.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

My work focused on the development of a number of standards for the CRA, the standard which I had most input to was the main horizontal standard for the CRA, ‘Cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements — General principles for cyber resilience’ which is being developed by CEN/CLC/JTC 13/WG 9 Project team One.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The CRA standards work on will continue for a number of years. This work is supported by a large number of Cybersecurity experts. To enable the CRA standards to best meet the

needs of the full range of consumers, experts in accessibility and usability standards will be required to work in parallel with them.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.etsi.org/about/10-events/2481-etsi-security-conference-oct2025#pane-9/

Fast delivery of initial contents for a range of standards across the AI Act standardisation request

Lauriane Aufrant

NLP researcher in academia, coordinating the institute's standardization roadmap, Inria

France

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CLC/JTC 21 "Artificial Intelligence"
CEN/CLC/JTC 21 WG 1 "Strategic Advisory Group"
CEN/CLC/JTC 21 WG 2 "Operational Aspects"
CEN/CLC/JTC 21 WG 3 "Engineering Aspects"
CEN/CLC/JTC 21 WG 4 "Foundational and societal aspects"
CEN/CLC/JTC 21 WG 5 "Joint standardization on Cybersecurity for AI systems")
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 "Artificial Intelligence"
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 WG 1 "Foundational standards"
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 WG 3 "Trustworthiness"
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 WG 5 "Computational approaches and computational characteristics of Artificial Intelligence systems"
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 JWG 2 "Testing of AI-based systems"
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 JWG 5 "Natural Language Processing")
AFNOR/CN IA "Artificial Intelligence"
ISO/TC 37 "Language and terminology"
ISO/TC 46 "Information and documentation"

Role

Convener of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 JWG 5 "Natural Language Processing"

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My efforts are currently focused on answering the standardization request that CEN-CENELEC JTC21 received from the European Commission in relation with the AI Act. Despite the delivery date having been extended from April 30 to August 31 2025, the harmonised standards are still way behind and the new date has been missed again, which is creating various downstream issues for the implementation of the AI Act, including public pressure for postponing its enforcement. There is therefore a need to boost progress, and I am working towards fast delivery of substantial text that can serve as initial content for various missing parts of the AI Act work programme, in order to spur subsequent contributions from other experts iterating over these texts. In that respect, I have set my priorities on the most technical standards (on datasets, bias, as well as evaluation methods for NLP and for computer vision), but am also conducting similar efforts on the standard for quality management system, as well as the AI Trustworthiness Framework standard (meant to become the main harmonised

standard for the AI Act), and more generally on the interplay of standards across the AI Act work programme.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Being an active member of many related working groups, I am in an ideal position to contribute on the technical alignment among those standards and refining their interplay. I do so as a core member of the CEN-CENELEC JTC 21/WG 1/Technical Coherence Forum, but also directly in specific standards: for instance in ISO/IEC 24970 on AI logging, in JTC 21's prEN 18229 on AI Trustworthiness Framework (part 1 for transparency / logging / human oversight, part 2 for accuracy and robustness), or prEN 18286 quality management system for regulatory purposes.

As for drafting activities, I have contributed substantial text and inputs to prEN 18283 "Concepts, measures and requirements for managing bias in AI systems" and ISO/IEC AWI 23282 (NLP evaluation) for initial drafting, as well as to ISO/IEC CD 24970 (logging) and prEN 18286 (regulatory QMS) in the frame of their ballot comment resolution processes. I have started contributing to the ballot comment resolution of ISO/IEC CD 4213 (performance metrics) which has just started. I have initiated efforts (especially collecting real-life examples) to ensure prEN 18284 "Quality and governance of datasets in AI" is widely applicable to the diversity of use cases and existing development practices. I have also delivered substantial material (draft text, conceptual framework, comprehensive gap analyses with the regulation, proposed content) for multiple items of prEN 18229 (AI Trustworthiness Framework).

Beyond technical contributions as an expert, my leadership responsibilities include being ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 Convenor for JWG 5 "Natural language processing", SC 42 & JTC 21 Editor for TR 23281, JTC 21 Editor for AWI 23282 (and SC42 Interim Editor during part of this fellowship), and liaison officer from JTC 21 to ISO/TC 37 "Language and terminology" and from SC 42 to ISO/TC 46 "Information and documentation". I am also providing informal support to the Editor of prEN 18288 and 18281 (computer vision tasks & CV evaluation).

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Harmonised standards are the preferred way for SMEs to comply with regulations under the New Legislative Framework (as the AI Act is) as they enable easy compliance with legal certainty and avoiding the need to resort to costly third-party legal support. The work is therefore to be developed with SMEs as one of the important targets. Furthermore, in the particular case of the AI Act, there are extra requirements in the EC standardisation request to consider the needs of SMEs/startups, and the AI Act Article about the quality management system includes special provisions for adaption of the obligations to the specificities of SMEs. In that context, I have pushed, first through comments in ballot then in the working group during comment resolution, for initiating dedicated discussions in that standard on those specificities with key stakeholders, which has proved beneficial even if still limited by the overall under-representation of SMEs in the standardisation work.

Impact on Society

My work serves as support to the preservation of consumer rights, by enabling more transparency, comparability, and clarity on the actual performance of AI systems in the market. Its societal impact also encompasses ethical aspects of AI such as human agency, for which appropriate use of explainability methods is a key enabler. More generally, it benefits the society at large through its interplay with the upcoming AI Act that will impact daily lives in Europe.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to the development of several specific AI/NLP related standards, including for instance

- ▶ ISO/IEC 24970 on AI logging, in JTC 21's prEN 18229 on AI Trustworthiness Framework (part 1 for transparency / logging / human oversight, part 2 for accuracy and robustness), or prEN 18286 quality management system for regulatory purposes.
- ▶ prEN 18283 "Concepts, measures and requirements for managing bias in AI systems".
- ▶ ISO/IEC AWI 23282 (NLP evaluation) for initial drafting, as well as to ISO/IEC CD 24970 (logging) and prEN 18286 (regulatory QMS).

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

To date, many of the experts involved in the European standards in support of the AI Act are actually employees of non-EU companies, promoting non-EU views. This has a severe impact on the ability to consolidate an EU position on those topics, and raises questions on whether we will at all succeed in establishing requirements to implement the AI Act. Both communication and funding need to be increased to enable the involvement of more experts who are not tied to non-EU interests but are actually promoting the EU views.

However, I would emphasize that new expert registration and funding are not by themselves sufficient to ensure adequate EU participation. CEN-CENELEC JTC21 has already known massive arrivals of experts without prior experience in standardisation, which overall led to more confusion, delays in the drafting (due to rerouting time to their upskilling) and sometimes even backtracking on the progress achieved on some documents (due to reopening prior agreements, or because new experts were not aware of the rationale of some prior actions). The addition of more EU experts therefore needs to be accompanied by close support for their upskilling, and especially training in standardisation work (its processes, its drafting rules, etc.). Some participants in CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 have started to provide this kind of support within the committee, but the CEN-CENELEC Technical Boards have subsequently forbidden to pursue such efforts, given that the role of a technical committee is solely to draft technical documents and not this kind of material.

The target date for the AI Act standardisation request was April 2025 for publication of the standards, which the European Commission has agreed to extend to August 2025, but these still have not been published. With the boost offered by my contribution (setting directions for the drafting, or directly new content, depending on the standard), I hope that new dynamics can develop now so that other experts can continue contributing in a more focused manner. But the work towards publication remains substantial, despite the increased time pressure from the upcoming entry into force of AI Act obligations (August 2026).

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475/x/catalogue/p/1/u/1/w/0/d/0>

 https://standards.cenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D

AI-Compliance: Proof of Concept and Refinement of the AI compliance guidelines standard

Luis Moran Abad

*ICT Standards Advisor, Luis Moran Abad
Spain*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

UNE-CTN71/SC40 ICT Governance and Service Management
UNE-CTN71/SC40 WG4 Adoption and Integration of Standards and Frameworks

Role

Secretary of UNE-CTN71/SC40 on ICT Governance and Service Management

Convenor of NE-CTN71/SC40 WG4 on Adoption and Integration of standards and bodies of knowledge.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Europe has not traditionally led the world in the development of new technologies, including AI. But having a system in place that facilitates compliance with regulatory requirements will make it easier for European organisations to adopt AI, its ethics and therefore improve their productivity.

Related to this several gaps persist, including:

- ▷ Existence of different sources of regulation and standardisation that generate diverse requirements.
- ▷ Lack of clarity in the interpretation of regulation, making it difficult to identify precise requirements.
- ▷ Continuous appearance of new regulations.
- ▷ Disconnect between regulation and practical application of requirements in AI systems.
- ▷ Increased difficulty for SMEs and VSMs to deal with this diversity and complexity.

In addition to these gaps, several challenges should be addressed:

- ▷ Difficulties in complying with the requirements of Local, European legislation and international standards, in translating legal requirements into concrete AI scenarios as well as in complying with ethical requirements in an AI environment with continuously learning algorithms.
- ▷ The cost of ensuring legislative compliance.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship supported the development of “Action 1” required by the EU Standards Rolling Plan for AI 2024, providing guidance on compliance through consolidation and integration of requirements. “This includes, in particular, the content of the EU AI Regulation proposal and the standardisation request on AI issued by the European Commission in 2023, as

well as the guidance set out in the 2021 review of the EU AI Coordinated Plan⁴. Moreover, our WG is working on a new standard (currently in project status, PNE): UNE-PNE-71407: "Guide to simplifying the adoption of regulations for compliance in systems that use artificial intelligence and other information technologies. Standard Technical Specification".

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

European small organisations (SMEs) and very small organisations (VSMEs) do not have the experts or economic resources to hire specialised AI consultants on compliance, so they must postpone the application of AI in their businesses. This generates a new delay in their innovation gap. The main opportunity for SMEs-VSMEs is their incorporation to a future AI-Compliance collectives: sectorial cluster type, laboratory of a City Hall and other potential movements of knowledge collectivisation.

Creating a standard to guide organisations and SMEs to facilitate compliance for AI implementations reduce the risk of sanctions by regulatory authorities and facilitates confidence that the use being made of AI systems is ethical, moral and legal.

Impact on Society

A new standard supports consolidating, integrating and optimising regulatory requirements and make compliance audits more efficient will be essential for the development of AI in Europe, and thus of European industry and welfare. This new standard will enable European organisations to leverage the full potential of AI while ensuring compliance with the various mandatory requirements. In doing so, this standard will enhance the competitiveness of European organisations.

In this way, the new standard will open the door to the competitiveness of European organisations by making AI compliance more efficient. The pillars of the new guidelines standard are:

- ▶ Converting different regulations and standards into a cloud of requirements.
- ▶ Consolidate and integrate these requirements into a specific set.
- ▶ To make the implementation of requirements more efficient.
- ▶ Reduce the cost and organisational effort of regulation compliance.
- ▶ Guidance on the management of specific requirements implementation projects.
- ▶ Reduce and optimise the number of internal and external audits.

My fellowship also contributed to the development of working methodologies in organisations aligned with the objectives of the European AI Office and its 'Regulation and Compliance' Unit.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, to a new standard - UNE-71407 EX:2026 "Guidance on simplifying regulatory adoption and compliance in systems using artificial intelligence and other information technologies. Standard Technical Specification"

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Once the new adoption standard for regulatory compliance in AI in the Spanish market has been officially published, the standard would have to be proposed as a new European standard.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.une.org/encuentra-tu-norma/comites-tecnicos-de-normalizacion/comite?c=CTN+71/SC+40

4 <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/artificial-intelligence-rp2024>

AIxPP: Artificial Intelligence framework to improve Professional Productivity. TS Standard

Javier Peris

*ICT Standards Senior Advisor, Consultant and Trainer, Business, Technology & Best Practices, S.L. (Business&Co.®)
Spain*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

UNE ICT mirror subcommittee for: ISO/IEC JTC 1 (ICT), subcommittee SC40 (ICT Management), WG5 Professional Productivity and WG7 Centres of Excellence (AI).

Role

Chair of UNE-CTN71/SC40 ITC Governance and Service Management

Convenor of WG7 of Excellence Centers

Chair of UNE-CTN309/SC1 Service Excellence

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship is a continuation of a previously funded activity and it supports the creation of an AI application framework standard is crucial to help organisations extract the full potential of AI's support for productivity and time management. ICT professionals find it very difficult to change personal and departmental work habits, as they are used to working without planning, always with urgencies and under stress.

Many managers still consider the way in which each person organises himself to do his job to be an intimate and individual matter. Also, the fragmentation of old productivity tools and the difficulty of integrating AI solutions into current work duties. While there is a lack of standards in the application of AI to support the work of professionals. The rapid evolution of AI technologies requires the standard that set an architecture and framework to be flexible and adaptable enough not to become quickly obsolete.

From the point of view of organisations, these require solutions that can be implemented at scale, ensuring consistency, data security, and AI governance, which can be a challenge for highly individualised tools. Also, the adoption of new AI-based tools in a change-resistance topic requires an intense top management commitment to lead its implementation. The use of AI to monitor or assist in time management raises questions about employee data privacy and the need for ethical and transparent use.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The targeted new standard will be focused on the human factor, on helping people to be happier and more effective in their work, while reducing their stress with the AI support. The new standard will combine aspects of time management, productivity, with intelligent automation. The standard will provide a high value to ICT professionals, teams and departments. By solving the severe productivity problem in ICT areas via AI automations, it

will help technology areas to develop their value-creating and transformational potential in their organisations.

Entering the vast field of humanistic and respectful treatment of professionals opens new frontiers for European and global standardisation. The new standard opens a new field of standardisation for ISO/IEC. In this domain of people and teams, many ICT-focused standards can be created that can be extended to other departments non-ICT. On the other hand, ISO/IEC's incursion into the standardisation of the humanistic perspective by solving deep-rooted problems of people in their work will enable SDOs to improve its image in society.

Furthermore, this initiative is fully aligned with the European standardisation strategy to have AI reliable projects as a business-transforming technology. This AIxPP standard to guide AI implementation in the ICT daily work will contribute to and align with European Commission "Rolling Plan for ICT standardisation 2024: Artificial Intelligence" and "European AI Act" by promoting trustworthy, human-centric AI adoption within operational processes. It supports the EU's strategic goals of fostering innovation while ensuring safety, transparency, and fundamental rights, particularly for SMEs and VSEs.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Create a standard reference model for AI productivity support and automation that helps ICT professionals, teams, and departments to be more productive, focused on value creation and with better time management. Will impulse SMEs and VSMEs competitiveness opportunities. Achieving high levels of performance in ICT areas will also allow SMEs to accelerate their digital transformation.

Impact on Society

Currently there are no standards dedicated directly on helping ICT professionals organise their lives. This standard will help professionals to better organise their goals and work, which will improve work-life balance. As professionals improve their organisational and productivity skills in ICT areas, this improvement will spread to other areas of the company and to society in general.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contributed the development of a new standard; UNE 71408 EX "Reference framework for the application of Artificial Intelligence to Professional Productivity and Time Management. Standard Technical Specification"

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The Artificial Intelligence sector is constantly evolving with new products and solutions. Therefore, this standard, which focuses on recommending different applications of AI in different horizontal or common aspects of work, needs to be reviewed and updated. Although the proposed reference model is agnostic with regard to existing AI products, the new capabilities that AI will bring will open up new opportunities for integration, assistance and automation of work.

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.une.org/encuentra-tu-norma/comites-tecnicos-de-normalizacion/comite/?c=CTN%2071/SC%2040

The EU Path to AI: AI Trust, AI Ethics, Sustainability AI, Fundamental Rights

Enrico Panai

*AI & Data Ethicist, Sardus France
France*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC21 Artificial Intelligence WG4 AI trustworthiness Framework
ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 Artificial Intelligence WG3 AI trustworthiness
AFNOR CNIA

Role

Convener of CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 WG4 “Foundational and societal aspects”;

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

As convener of WG4 in JTC21, I play a pivotal role in shaping the committee’s strategic direction, steering discussions, fostering consensus, and advancing standardisation efforts within our technical remit. This position builds on my prior contributions, which have been recognised and supported by StandICT.eu 2026 through several funding batches. My ongoing engagement enables me to extend my influence on standards, grounded in the demonstrable impact of my previous work.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

In my leadership role, I contribute to several ongoing standardisation projects:

- ▶ AI Trustworthiness Framework – prEN 18229: Standard defining terminology, concepts, and core requirements for AI trustworthiness, covering logging, transparency, human oversight, accuracy, and robustness. Supports compliance with the EU AI Act and aligns with European Commission priorities. The project is going to be split in part 1 and part 2. Enquiry of part 1 launch is imminent.
- ▶ Environmentally Sustainable AI – JT021010: Improves AI energy efficiency through optimised algorithms and energy-efficient pre-trained modules.
- ▶ Sustainable AI – Guidelines and Metrics – JT021035: Establishes metrics for efficient, resource-aware AI use. Candidate for NWIP ballot soon.
- ▶ Competence Requirements for Professional AI Ethicists – JT021019: Defines qualifications for AI ethicists to address the lack of a standard framework, ensuring consistent ethics integration. Enquiry launch imminent.
- ▶ Guidance for Upskilling Organisations – JT021033: Builds essential ethical skills in workforces to embed ethics in AI development, deployment, and governance.
- ▶ Guidelines on Tools for Ethical Issues – JT021034: Creates tools to manage AI ethical issues, adapting global ICT tools to European values and regulations.
- ▶ Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment – JT021026: Develops Human Rights Impact Assessments for AI in line with EU, OSCE, ITU, and UNESCO commitments.

- ▷ Risk Management in Critical Digital Infrastructure (pending number): Supports AI risk management in critical infrastructure with sector-specific methods, hazard taxonomy, and guidance, complementing prEN AI Risk Management.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The AI Trustworthiness Framework plays a key role in enabling the effective implementation of the EU AI Act, setting essential standards that help organisations meet legal obligations. Ethical standards are particularly important for SMEs, providing clear guidance to navigate uncertainties in AI adoption. They foster responsible innovation by enabling SMEs to engage qualified ethicists, choose suitable tools, and strengthen ethical awareness. Also, sustainable AI initiatives equip organisations for forthcoming EU environmental requirements, advancing the development of energy-efficient, environmentally responsible AI systems to ensure future regulatory compliance.

Impact on Society

The different targeted standards have a different societal impact:

- ▷ AI Trustworthiness Framework (prEN 18229): (Part 1 and Part 2) Establishes terminology, concepts, and requirements for AI trustworthiness, addressing five of the ten SRs. Facilitates AI Act compliance and meets varied stakeholder needs.
- ▷ Environmentally Sustainable AI (JT021010): Cuts AI energy consumption—particularly in neural networks—through more efficient algorithms and pre-trained models, in line with EU climate neutrality targets.
- ▷ Transparency Taxonomy of AI Systems (JT021022): Creates a structured framework to enhance transparency, accountability, and comparability across AI systems.
- ▷ Upskilling on AI Ethics (JT021033) & Ethical Management Guidelines (JT021034): Provide tools and guidance to embed ethical and social considerations throughout the AI lifecycle.
- ▷ Sustainable AI – Guidelines and Metrics (JT021035): Defines KPIs to assess and minimise AI's environmental impact, promoting sustainable practices.
- ▷ Impact Assessment and Fundamental Rights (JT021026): Identifies and mitigates risks to fundamental rights, ensuring AI systems align with EU values.
- ▷ Risk Management in Critical Digital Infrastructure (pending): Delivers tailored methodologies, use cases, and hazard taxonomies to manage AI risks in critical systems, complementing prEN AI Risk Management.
- ▷ AI-Enhanced Nudging (JT021003): Addresses ethical risks of AI-driven nudges, safeguarding vulnerable groups and preserving public trust.
- ▷ Competence Requirements for AI Ethicists (JT021019): Defines core skills and knowledge for AI ethicists to ensure effective ethical integration in AI systems..

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I have contributed to a series of new standards as listed here above.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The complexity of fundamental and societal aspects calls for greater multidisciplinary expertise within the group to deliver well-rounded, effective, and inclusive standardisation outcomes.

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.cenelec.eu/areas-of-work/cen-cenelec-topics/artificial-intelligence/

Trustworthy AI infrastructure – Towards AI for infrastructure and Infrastructure for AI

Gyu Myoung Lee

*Research director and international standardization, Liverpool John Moores University
United Kingdom*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ITU-T SG13 (Future Networks) Q16 (Future networks: Trustworthy and quantum enhanced networking and services)
ITU-TSG20 (Internet of Things, digital twins and smart sustainable cities and communities) Q4 (Data analytics, sharing, processing and management, including big data aspects, of Internet of Things (IoT) and smart sustainable cities and communities (SSC&C))
ITU-T Focus Group on Artificial Intelligence Native for Telecommunication Networks (FG AINN)

Role

Convenor (JCG-Trust)

Vice Chair (ITU-T FG-AINN)

Rapporteur (ITU-T SG13 Q16, SG20 Q4),

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship supports the development of a standardized framework for trustworthy, AI-native digital infrastructure by moving away from centralized, opaque architectures toward decentralized, composable, and transparent platforms. It addresses key challenges in current digital ecosystems, such as fragmentation, centralization, and lack of trust, with priorities including the development of AI-native composable infrastructure that embeds transparency, privacy, and accountability; the advancement of standards for federated AI, digital twin interoperability, and decentralized identity; and the resolution of gaps in trustworthy execution and governance to reduce Europe's dependency on non-European platforms. The fellowship further seeks to enable federated, decentralized AI, ensure data sovereignty, and align composable infrastructure with European values of privacy, fairness, and transparency. These standardisation efforts are very significant in facilitating the timely adoption of emerging technologies with a global, interoperable standard for future AI infrastructure.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The project contributes to gap analysis, preliminary standardization, and the development of standards, including editorship of several draft ITU-T documents (Recommendation, Supplement, Deliverable, etc.) for a reference implementation of trustworthy AI infrastructure, while also establishing a meta-architecture for the future Internet and advancing standardization efforts in organizations such as ITU-T. More specifically, the funded application supports ICT standards on trustworthy AI infrastructure, engaging with

key standards analysis such as ITU-T Y.3052–Y.3056 (trust provisioning frameworks), ISO/IEC 24028 (trustworthiness in AI), ISO/IEC 30173 (digital twins), W3C Decentralized Identifiers and Verifiable Credentials, ETSI ENI 005 (AI-native networks), and GAIA-X data sovereignty frameworks.

It actively contributes to shaping new recommendations and metamodels for trustworthy, AI-driven infrastructure, with a focus on distributed identity, federated learning, and composable service orchestration, ultimately aiming to provide comprehensive guidance for future standardization in trustworthy AI infrastructure. To do so, I am currently involved in developing standardization roadmap on trust technologies in ITU-T SG13 and SG20 as Co-Convenor of JCG-Trust in ITU-T as well as having a leading role in AI related standardization as Vice-Chair of ITU-T FG-AINN and Rapporteur of Q4/20.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

By enabling open, interoperable, and composable infrastructure, the project supports SME participation, fosters innovation, and drives human-centric, privacy-compliant digital services for European society. Its outcomes will empower key sectors such as smart cities, manufacturing, energy, and healthcare to deploy AI-powered, decentralized services with built-in trust and autonomy, accelerating the development of data-driven business models and open marketplaces that deliver user-centric and adaptive digital experiences. Moreover, the project strengthens European leadership in ethical and human-centric AI by providing a blueprint for technical standards that embed transparency, privacy, fairness, and sustainability by design.

Impact on Society

The accelerating integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into all layers of our digital society is transforming how services, data, and infrastructure operate. However, as AI systems become more pervasive, there is a growing need to ensure that the underlying infrastructure is not only intelligent, but also trustworthy, interoperable, secure, and aligned with human-centric values. This activity directly addresses that need by proposing a reference architecture and standardisation framework for trustworthy AI-native infrastructure, enabling both “AI for infrastructure” and “infrastructure for AI”.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

I am contributing to ITU-T standardization on trustworthy AI infrastructure. Examples:

- ▶ Y.TRUST-AI, Overview of trust provisioning for networks and services using AI technologies
- ▶ Y.support-trust-guide, Guideline for standardization of trust technologies in ITU-T SG13
- ▶ Y.support-trust-roadmap, Standardization roadmap on trustworthy networking and services for study period 2025
- ▶ Y.trust-MVInf-fr, Framework of a trustworthy metaverse infrastructure -Q4/20 (IoT Trust)
- ▶ Supplement to Y.4000-series – Concepts and perspectives of trust in IoT, digital twins and smart sustainable cities and communities
- ▶ Y.IoT-FETA, Framework for Ensuring Trust of AI Data across Distributed Systems for Intelligent IoT Services - FG-AINN deliverables on AI native telecommunication networks

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Most items have recently been created as new work items to initiate relevant standardisation activities. Gap analysis and preliminary efforts to establish a concrete direction for future standardisation have been conducted, and relevant technical details are being investigated.

Online references related to the fellowship work

- ITU-T SG13 - Future networks and emerging network technologies: <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/studygroups/2025-2028/13/Pages/default.aspx>
- Q16/13 - Future networks: Trustworthy and quantum enhanced networking and services: <https://www.itu.int/net4/ITU-T/lists/q-text.aspx?Group=13&Period=18&QNo=16&Lang=en>
- ITU-T SG20 - Internet of Things, digital twins and smart sustainable cities and communities: <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/studygroups/2025-2028/20/Pages/default.aspx>
- Q4/20 - Data analytics, sharing, processing and management, including big data aspects, of Internet of Things (IoT) and smart sustainable cities and communities (SSC&C): <https://www.itu.int/net4/ITU-T/lists/q-text.aspx?Group=20&Period=18&QNo=4&Lang=en>
- JCG-Trust (Joint Correspondence Group on Trust): <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/jcg/trust/Pages/default.aspx>
- FG-AINN (Focus Group on Artificial Intelligence Native for Telecommunication Networks): <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/focusgroups/ainn/Pages/default.aspx>

Co-editing AI Trustworthiness Framework prEN 18229 and coordinating across JTC21 Working Groups

Luca Nannini

*Senior AI Policy & Standards Specialist, Piccadilly Labs
Spain*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC21 Artificial Intelligence
CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG1 - Strategic Advisory Group
CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG2 - Operational Aspects of AI Systems
CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG3 - Engineering Aspects
CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG4 - AI Trustworthiness
CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 - Cybersecurity

Role

Editor of EN AI Trustworthiness Framework (JT021008) at CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 WG4
Expert member in other WGs

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The critical gap addressed is leading technical development of Accuracy and Robustness specifications within EN AI Trustworthiness Framework Part II while coordinating overall framework progression toward Enquiry. As demonstrated through N1106 “Roadmap to ENQ” and N1050 “Accuracy & Robustness Status & Roadmap,” this editorial leadership provides systematic coordination of complex technical definitions across international expert communities. The robustness clause particularly required building conceptual clarity from foundational principles through expert consensus processes.

In this sense, the primary priority involved coordinating expert consensus for Part II (accuracy/robustness) while ensuring Part I (logging, transparency, human oversight) achieved Enquiry readiness. My editorial work through N1106 synthesized comprehensive ENQ preparation strategy including timeline management, clause-by-clause gap analysis, cross-WG coordination mechanisms, and expert contribution guidance aligned with CEN/CENELEC IR3 and hEN checklist requirements. This coordination ensures framework development meets Commission harmonization timeline requirements while maintaining technical excellence.

The most complex challenge involved managing conceptual framework consensus for robustness definitions (N1030 evaluation) while coordinating intensive September-October ENQ preparation activities. Editorial responsibilities extended beyond typical participation to include producing consolidated tracked-change text (N1111), developing expert guidance tools (N1124), facilitating cross-WG dependencies with EN Risk and Cybersecurity standards, and maintaining systematic documentation through comprehensive meeting minutes. The challenge of coordinating diverse international stakeholder perspectives toward presumption of conformity requirements while managing compressed timelines demanded sustained editorial leadership and strategic coordination capabilities.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

As Editor of EN AI Trustworthiness Framework Part II (JT021008-2, prEN 18229-2), I directly shape European approaches to AI accuracy and robustness that will influence global AI governance. The editorial achievement of N1106 “Roadmap to ENQ” represents comprehensive synthesis coordinating Enquiry preparation across all framework components, establishing strategic coordination mechanisms essential for harmonized standard development.

Also, I support the development of JT021008-2 (prEN 18229-2 - EN AI Trustworthiness Framework Part II: Accuracy and Robustness) while coordinating overall framework progression including JT021008-1 (prEN 18229-1 - Part I: Logging, Transparency, Human Oversight).

As well as I contribute to JT021039 (AI Quality Management System), JT021024 (AI Risk Management), JT021029 (AI Cybersecurity Specifications)

The standards development directly supports presumption of conformity pathways under the EU AI Act, enabling European SMEs to demonstrate compliance through standardized approaches. N1106 coordination work positions Part I for Enquiry submission while maintaining Part II development momentum

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The editorial leadership of EN AI Trustworthiness Framework Part II directly supports European SMEs through Articles 62-63 AI Act provisions for SME assistance. The standard provides SMEs with clear, pre-endorsed technical specifications for meeting AI Act accuracy and robustness requirements, reducing compliance costs and legal uncertainty. The harmonization documentation coordinated through editorial work enables SMEs to achieve presumption of conformity through standardized approaches rather than expensive individual assessments.

Impact on Society

I can see several societal impacts with the engaged standardisation activities:

- ▶ AI Accuracy and Robustness Standards: As Editor of EN AI Trustworthiness Framework Part II, my work directly supports European citizens' rights to accurate and robust AI systems. The standard establishes technical requirements ensuring AI systems deployed across the EU meet rigorous accuracy standards and maintain performance across operational conditions, protecting citizens from unreliable algorithmic decision-making in high-risk contexts.
- ▶ SME Innovation Ecosystem: The editorial leadership through N1106 coordination enables European SMEs to compete effectively in AI markets by providing clear compliance pathways rather than costly regulatory uncertainty. This supports innovation while ensuring responsible AI deployment protecting European citizens.
- ▶ European Leadership in Global AI Governance: The editorial role positions European values-based approaches to AI accuracy and robustness for global influence. The framework embeds principles of reliability, trustworthiness, and accountability into technical specifications that influence international AI standardization discussions.
- ▶ Consumer Protection Framework: The cross-WG coordination through N1106 ensures AI standards address consumer concerns around system reliability, performance consistency, and safety while remaining technically implementable. This balance protects European consumers while supporting technological advancement and maintaining Europe's competitive position in global AI markets.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, as mentioned above, I am the editor of CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 WG4 - EN AI Trustworthiness Framework prEN 18229.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The appointment as Editor of EN AI Trustworthiness Framework Part II marks a critical maturation phase requiring sustained editorial leadership through Enquiry and Comment Resolution Meeting (CRM) periods. The framework splitting necessitates enhanced coordination to maintain technical coherence across components, as demonstrated through N1106 comprehensive coordination strategy. Continued investment in editorial expertise and cross-WG coordination mechanisms is essential for meeting the European Commission's timeline requirements while ensuring technical excellence and presumption of conformity status. The harmonisation documentation development requires sustained expert engagement coordinated through editorial leadership. The intensive September-October 2025 period demonstrated the level of coordination required, with weekly meetings, systematic documentation, and strategic stakeholder management essential for progress. International coordination activities through Vienna Agreement frameworks need continued support to ensure European leadership in global AI standardization discussions

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.cenelec.eu/areas-of-work/cen-cenelec-topics/artificial-intelligence/

Artificial Intelligence Standardisation (Accuracy, Cybersecurity and other topics)

James Davenport

*Professor of Information Technology, University of Bath
United Kingdom*

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC21 Artificial Intelligence WG3 Engineering Aspects
CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 Cybersecurity

Role (chair, convenor, member)

Convenor of CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG3 Engineering Aspects

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

There is currently no standard addressing the cybersecurity of AI systems at the level necessary. ISO-IEC's 27090 contains no requirements. Hence JTC21 is developing a Cybersecurity of AI standard with requirements, so I contribute to that in JTC21/WG5.

There are many gaps at the technical level in AI standards and I convene JTC21 WG3 which looks at these gaps. I am currently working on a detailed alignment of the standards being developed against the requirements in Articles 10 and 15 of the EU AI Act. WG4 is looking at Article 13, but there is overlap (for example 10 and 13 both mention "bias") and I lead for WG3 here.

There are many issues with the overlap of standards, which shows up in their mathematical content. I was asked at SC42 to resolve a mathematical issue in JWG2, but the same issue also came up in JWG4 and WG3, and I have asked the convenors to check for overlap. The mathematics is not currently well-described, and I am working with an Indian colleague to improve this.

This project faces two key challenges that are firstly the shortage of experts to which I am trying to contribute by doing recruiting in the UK's NSB and at conferences. Secondly, this work faces pressure, at both JTC 21 and ISO-IEC, by representatives of various countries who happen to be employed by multinational companies to delay these standards, and remove any formal requirements.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship supports my engagement as a convenor of CEN/CENELEC JTC21/WG3. This covers follow up of different relevant standardisation projects, such as ISO-IEC TR 23281, AWI 23282 (NLP), 24029 series (Robustness), 24970 (logging), 42012 (Framework for characterizing AI system methods and capabilities) and talking about the JTC 21 standards that are relevant.

In CEN/CENELEC JTC21 I am largely looking at the standards

- ▷ Artificial Intelligence - Taxonomy of AI tasks in computer vision
- ▷ Artificial Intelligence – Evaluation methods for accurate computer vision systems
- ▷ Artificial Intelligence - Concepts, measures and requirements for managing bias in AI systems

- ▷ Artificial Intelligence -- Quality and governance of datasets in AI
- ▷ Artificial intelligence - Cybersecurity specifications for AI Systems

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Many of these standards, e.g. Bias, impact society. In terms of SMEs, I have been closely associated with a software SME, and always ask myself how this SME would be impacted. I am also sensitive to the views of one of my editors who is CTO of an Austrian SME.

Impact on Society

Artificial Intelligence has numerous societal implications, particularly around implicit biases. Machine Learning learns from data which reflects the society we have (or had if the data is historic) rather than the society we believe we have, or wish we have. Hence my WG is working on a Bias standard, dealing operationally with detection and mitigation, to build on the excellent work done in ISO-IEC, to which I have contributed. Furthermore, I frequently give interviews with media (typically UK media) on AI. I have also spoken on AI standardisation at relevant subject-matter conferences (on Natural Language Processing and Symbolic Methods)

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Not directly, as this fellowship supports my leadership role within CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG3.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

To continue these standardisation efforts successfully, more European experts are needed. I have made appeals at BSI, and asked my colleagues to do the same at other NSBs, with limited success. I have also made appeals at relevant conferences, again limited success. But even if we had the experts, there is still quite a lengthy process to publication.

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.cencenelec.eu/areas-of-work/cen-cenelec-topics/artificial-intelligence/

<https://jtc21.eu/working-groups/>

Final Adoption of Big Earth Datacube standard

Peter Baumann

Scientist, *rasdaman GmbH*
Germany

Sector

Data interoperability

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO TC211 Geographic information / Geographics WG6 Geographic Imagery
OGC Coverages SWG

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Never before it was so fast and cheap way to obtain information about land, water, atmosphere, as well as human impact on it. In Europe, for example, the Copernicus satellite family provides the fundament for insight on our planet, together with long climate timeseries and further data, such as elevation models. For such Big Earth Data the concept of spatio-temporal datacubes is an established cornerstone, in OGC, ISO, and EU INSPIRE standardisation modelled as “coverages”.

For powerful, user-friendly, interoperable services a technically sound coverage standards suite is indispensable. The ISO/OGC suite of the coverage data and service model is instrumental for easy, interoperable handling of these data, and a who’s who of major open-source and proprietary geo tools support these standards. For example, the legal framework for a common European spatial data infrastructure, INSPIRE, has adopted CIS as its basis.

In summary, this standards work is of highest practical relevance and visibility, with significant impact on geo data infrastructures and, ultimately, increased understanding of our planet and the impact we have on it, but also common day-to-day use of insight from geo data.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship focused on finalising the revision of ISO TC211 19123-2. The 19123-2 specification, which I am the author of, was finalized and submitted to ISO secretariat which started the FDIS ballot, which is the last stage before ultimate adoption. This finalisation work included reaction on delegation comments from the last (DIS) vote, final editing, and preparing material (eg, graphics) in the format ISO secretariat expects

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

SMEs typically provide niche products which are accepted by the market only if they convey strong interoperability. The 19123-2 standard accomplishes this for images, image

timeseries, and further Earth data. Spatio-temporal Earth data, as standardized with 19123-2, are instrumental for manifold purposes, such as environmental monitoring, disaster management, and many more.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I lead the revision of 1 ISO TC211 19123-2.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The FDIS ballot phase will run until January 2026. Following adoption by ISO in Jan 2025, OGC will want to adopt 19123-2 as CIS 1.2. This needs to be initiated, driven, and completed actively.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://committee.iso.org/sites/tc211/home/projects/projects---complete-list/iso-19123-2.html>

Coordinate the ISO-IEC/SC7 Standards in the area of Techniques for Specifying IT Systems

Nicolas Treves
Chairman, RDT Consulting
France

Sector

Data interoperability

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO-IEC/JTC1/SC7 Software and systems engineering WG19
Techniques for Specifying IT Systems

Role

Convenor of ISO-IEC/JTC1/SC7/WG19

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This was a short-term fellowship supporting my convensorship. During the period, I contributed to the following activities:

- ▶ Ensuring the sustainability of the standards developed within the IEC/JTC1/SC7/WG19 working group,
- ▶ Identifying existing difficulties and proposing solutions to resolve them,
- ▶ Raising awareness among the various members of the working group of the need to use OSD in future standards development,
- ▶ Coordinating actions with the WG19 secretary and reporting to the SC7 secretariat.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Three standards are currently on progress in this working group:

- ▶ ISO/IEC 15909:2 is in the preliminary revision phase. A committee draft (CD) is expected by mid-2026. The use of OSD for the development of this new version is now mandatory, and a training program is being organized by ISO and AFNOR. I recently obtained, along with the project editor, the rights to use OSD from the ISO technical team leader .
- ▶ A CD for ISO/IEC 20499 scheduled for delivery in November, was provided on October 29 by the project editor. Members of WG19 are now invited to comment on this CD. My role is to ensure the collection of comments and to provide my own.

Other opportunities, such as the development of a machine-readable standard under the ISO-IEC SMART initiative, are being considered, but according to those in charge of this plan, OSD stabilization is required first.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The standards considered in WG19 are of great interest to the EU airspace, transportation, aviation, defence, energy and telecommunications industries, as well as for the universities that have contact with IT tools development companies in the area of systems formal verification. The use of these standards could have an impact on EU SMEs, particularly on IT

tools editors, but it is not a priority.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, in my leadership position I contribute to the development of several new standards, as described here above.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I continue my work within the WG as its convener beyond this fellowship ensuring that the running projects are finalised as planned and managing the liaisons with other group members.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/45086.html

EUDI Wallet (eIDAS2) held personal data access control

Jan Lindquist

Privacy and Security Standards Expert, Linaltec AB
Sweden*

Sector

Electronic identification and trust services (including e-signature)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/TC 224 WG 20 – European Digital Identity Wallet
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG 5 – Identity Management and Privacy Technologies
SIS/TK318 AG5 – Swedish national committee on privacy and security standards

Role

Chair of SIS/TK 318 AG5

Lead editor at ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG 5

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship addresses two key standardisation gaps and one strategic priority in advancing privacy and access control for the EUDI Wallet.

- ▶ Lack of harmonised access control requirements across actors: While eIDAS2 mandates purpose limitation and data minimisation, there is currently no consistent standard governing how access control is enforced across issuers, wallets, and relying parties. In CEN/TC 224 WG20, I am leading the development of a wallet-side access control specification. This work has revealed that key privacy requirements — such as data sensitivity classification and retention control — are insufficiently addressed on the issuer and relying party sides. I have developed a detailed analysis of disclosure policy enforcement, which is now being reviewed by ETSI ESI for possible complementary standardisation work.
- ▶ Limited focus on anticipatory risk and fraud mitigation: Current digital identity standards lack structured approaches for mitigating emerging misuse and fraud scenarios. Within WG20, I initiated risk discussions focused on transparency-by-design and fraud resilience. These efforts are increasingly relevant in the context of ENISA's EUDI Wallet certification scheme, where forward-looking safeguards are essential.

The priority is to Operationalise all GDPR lawful bases, and I continue to lead the revision of ISO/IEC 27560, expanding it from a consent-only model to cover all lawful bases under the GDPR. While this is a known limitation, sustained editorial and stakeholder engagement is required to ensure its regulatory relevance, technical clarity, and cross-sector adoption.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship supports the development of privacy-enhancing and legally aligned standards for digital identity in the EU.

As lead editor, I am revising ISO/IEC 27560 to support all GDPR lawful bases, ensuring that consent and other legal grounds for processing are represented in structured, interoperable

records. The revision is currently in the Committee Draft (CD) ballot phase.

I am also advancing a new CEN/TC 224 WG20 standard on access control for EUDI Wallet attributes. The third working draft received 185 comments, which are now being addressed in the next revision.

Both standards are aligned with the GDPR, Data Governance Act, and eIDAS2, directly contributing to EU goals on lawful processing, transparency, and digital trust. The work is coordinated with ETSI ESI (via liaison role), and the access control standard has been identified by ENISA as a candidate input for the EUDI Wallet certification framework.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

My work simplifies GDPR compliance for European SMEs by developing standards that make privacy receipts and access control both practical and cost-effective. By embedding lawful bases and user-facing transparency into consent and data access records, SMEs can demonstrate accountability while reducing legal risk. For society, this promotes stronger digital rights, user agency, and trust in the EUDI Wallet ecosystem.

Impact on Society

My work supports fundamental societal values by helping define how citizens can safely and transparently share their personal data through the European Digital Identity (EUDI) Wallet. At the heart of this is the development of access control standards that ensure individuals are not just passive data subjects, but active participants who can decide what data is shared, with whom, under what conditions, and for what declared purpose.

By enabling these controls through enforceable, machine-readable policies, the standard empowers users to exercise real agency over their digital identity—moving beyond consent screens toward meaningful privacy protections embedded in the architecture of the wallet itself. This aligns with the EU's commitment to privacy, data minimisation, and purpose limitation under the GDPR.

The work also supports societal inclusion by ensuring that access control mechanisms are transparent and usable, helping citizens understand their rights and obligations, while also simplifying compliance for service providers. The inclusion of ISO/IEC 27560 in this framework ensures that all lawful bases for processing—not just consent—are clearly documented and traceable, which is especially important for use cases like healthcare, education, or public services.

Importantly, the open availability of ISO/IEC 27560 as a free standard lowers the barrier for adoption, supporting uptake by public administrations, SMEs, and civil society. This ensures that privacy-enhancing technologies are not limited to large commercial actors, but can benefit all layers of European society.

Overall, this work contributes to a more trustworthy, transparent, and citizen-centric digital identity ecosystem—one that upholds European values while supporting innovation, cross-border interoperability, and regulatory alignment.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. My project contributed to the development of a new access control standard under CEN/TC 224 WG20, and it also helped identify alignment gaps with the EUDI Wallet Implementation Act. These were presented to SRAGH and shared with ETSI ESI to address weaknesses in risk coverage and operational requirements. The work is informing discussion on a proposed new framework for EUDIW Supporting Services policy requirements and conformity assessment based on EN 319 401 and EN 319 403-1. Access control is now positioned as a foundational input to this emerging layer of trust services, extending its role beyond the wallet into supporting certification and compliance architecture.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I strongly recommend continuation of the current standardisation efforts on both the CEN/TC 224 WG20 Access Control specification and the ISO/IEC 27560 revision. These standards address critical gaps in the operationalisation of digital identity under eIDAS2, particularly around how personal data can be accessed, disclosed, and processed in a lawful and transparent manner.

The WG20 access control standard is essential to ensure that EUDI Wallet implementations respect the principle of purpose limitation, allowing only authorised access to user data based on declared, enforceable conditions. With over 180 expert comments received, the draft is undergoing significant refinement and consensus-building. Continued support is necessary to mature this work into a Committee Draft and prepare it for potential referencing in ENISA's certification framework.

For ISO/IEC 27560, expanding the scope beyond consent to include all GDPR lawful bases enables broader applicability across public and private sectors. Its recent designation as a freely accessible standard also increases its societal and institutional impact. However, further work is needed to finalise the revision and ensure it is implemented consistently across jurisdictions.

In addition, ongoing coordination across SDOs—particularly between CEN, ETSI ESI, and ISO—is vital to avoid fragmentation and ensure interoperability. Continued action will help bridge technical development with EU policy goals, notably in relation to the Digital Identity Framework, GDPR compliance, and the upcoming Data Governance Act and AI Act.

Given the rising importance of digital identity in cross-border services, public sector digitisation, and user empowerment, completing and aligning these standards is not only technically important—it is a strategic priority for safeguarding European digital sovereignty and user trust.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/standard/91775.html>

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:6205,25&cs=1BEC25E62B2D3FAE470A24A21A7315A0B

ISCC and other methods for binding in information identification

Kira C. Lemke
COO, Craft AG
Germany

Sector

Electronic identification and trust services (including e-signature)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 46/SC9 Identification and description WG 18 International Standard Content Code (ISCC) a

Role

Convener of ISO/TC 46/SC9/WG18

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

In the framework of this fellowship, I worked on a Technical Report (TR) that addresses critical gaps and challenges in the international standards landscape for digital content identification and binding mechanisms.

The absence of a common terminology across standardisation communities poses a major challenge. Different communities use inconsistent language when describing how content is connected with its metadata or other associated information. Whereas the C2PA initiative uses its own distinct terminology, other standardisation communities (e.g. W3C or OAIS) have different interpretations of what bindings mean. This terminological divergence leads to interoperability and mutual understanding barriers. The TR is establishing a comprehensive taxonomy that provides a neutral reference framework for multiple standardisation efforts, facilitating clearer communication across standardisation communities.

A gap the TR is addressing, is the limited comprehension of how binding mechanisms respond to content transformations. Digital content undergoes frequent alterations through compression, format conversion, and editing. Traditional identifier systems often fail when these changes occur, particularly when embedded metadata is stripped. The Working Group systematically analyses characteristics and limitations of different binding approaches, from cryptographic hashing to robust fingerprinting to watermarking techniques. This analysis will help stakeholders to make informed architectural decisions tailored to their specific requirements.

Moreover, the fellowship further contributes to positioning the recently published ISCC standard (ISO 24138:2024) within a broader global context. The TR serves as an educational resource, helping stakeholders understand how similarity-preserving identification methods complement established identification systems and address emerging needs in content provenance and authenticity verification, particularly relevant with current growth of AI-generated content.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The fellowship contributes to the ICT standards landscape by supporting the development of a Technical Report (TR) that establishes a common terminology and a conceptual framework for understanding binding mechanisms in digital content identification.

My Working Group previously developed ISO 24138:2024, the ISCC, a similarity-preserving content-derived identifier, enabling standardised multi-modal identification across text,

image, audio and video content formats. The TR builds on this foundation and explores how content-derived identification works within the broader ecosystem of binding mechanisms. By analysing particular characteristics, robustness properties, and implementation requirements of different binding mechanisms, the TR offers guidance aimed at enabling the interoperability among heterogeneous identification systems.

The TR also addresses ISO/DIS 22144, which describes the technical aspects of the C2PA architecture, known as Content Credentials. The TR provides broader context for understanding binding concepts and includes disambiguation of terminology around C2PA's specific usage of terms, notably "hard binding" (cryptographic hashes) and "soft binding" (similarity-preserving hashes or watermarks surviving certain transformations). Our group's liaison relationship with ISO/TC 171/SC 2 facilitates coordination between our respective activities.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The TR will guide SMEs in understanding binding mechanisms: structural (metadata embedding), semantic (descriptive relationships), algorithmic (hashes, content-derived identifiers), and resolvable (URLs, DOIs).

In terms of applications, an Italian start-up, amlet.ai, adopted ISCC (one algorithmic binding approach examined in the TR) for their TDM registry. Also, Dutch liccium.com implements ISCC for decentralized content registration and rights management. Estonian valunode.com uses ISCC in their decentralised content management solutions. These implementations exemplify relevance across AI/TDM, rights management, and digital content workflows.

In terms of Impact, the TR clarifies how embedding, watermarking, fingerprinting, and cryptographic approaches differ in robustness and workflow requirements, helping SMEs make informed decisions and build expertise. Content-derived methods computing identifiers locally enable GDPR-compliant implementations without centralised tracking, supporting digital sovereignty.

Impact on Society

I can see several societal impacts for this work, including:

- ▶ Digital Trust and Information Integrity: The TR systematically documents capabilities and limitations of different content binding mechanisms and enables an informed selection of appropriate trust mechanisms, critical for democratic processes and media trust in the AI era.
- ▶ Data Sovereignty and Privacy: The analysis of decentralised identification methods directly supports European digital sovereignty principles and GDPR compliance. By documenting alternatives to centralised tracking, the work enables implementations where rightsholders maintain control over digital assets while supporting privacy-by-design standards, addressing fundamental European values around data protection.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

No. This fellowship focused on the development of the technical report, described here above, and it serves as an educational resource.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The TR remains in active development with completion expected in Q2/2026. Outstanding sections include detailed analysis of fingerprinting-based methods and additional verification mechanisms. The next meeting in the first week of December 2025 is specifically planned to advance these remaining components.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/48836.html>

Advancing IoT Standards for Smart Irrigation in Sustainable Agriculture

Endrit Ameti

Chief Executive Officer, Biotech
Kosovo

Sector

Internet of Things (IoT)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

FAO – Digital Agriculture Working Group (AKIS Platform)

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The focus of my fellowship was to support the Integration of IoT, data interoperability, and standardisation practices into agricultural digital transformation frameworks.

The main gaps addressed through this fellowship were the lack of national policy alignment, weak participation in standardisation processes, and limited awareness of ICT interoperability frameworks in the Western Balkans, particularly Kosovo. Until recently, standardisation in agriculture was not part of the national digitalisation agenda, leaving many innovations fragmented and incompatible with EU frameworks.

In this context, I contributed to the national consultation and standardisation alignment process that shaped the Digital Agriculture Programme and Action Plan 2025–2028 in Kosovo, referencing European standards such as SAFE4Agri, ETSI SAREF4Agri, and ISO/IEC 30141.

Through the fellowship, I helped initiate dialogue between national authorities, FAO–AKIS, and regional organisations to begin integrating ICT standardisation principles into agriculture policy.

The challenge was not only technical but also institutional and educational — to convince policymakers and agricultural associations of the value of adopting open European standards. As one of the first developers to successfully deploy smart irrigation IoT solutions in Kosovo, I used practical examples to demonstrate the benefits of standardisation and its role in improving interoperability, transparency, and SME innovation.

This fellowship therefore contributed to bridging the policy gap between innovation and regulation, ensuring that Western Balkan countries begin integrating EU ICT standardisation frameworks into their national digital-agriculture strategies.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

During the fellowship, I worked on disseminating and contextualising several key ICT standards:

- ▶ ETSI SAREF4Agri – enabling semantic interoperability between sensors, controllers, and cloud platforms;
- ▶ ISO/IEC 30141 – providing a scalable IoT reference architecture for agriculture and rural monitoring systems;

- ▶ SAFE4Agri – supporting safety, data integrity, and reliability in IoT-based farming and irrigation;
- ▶ LoRaWAN and MQTT protocols – ensuring secure and efficient data communication for low-power devices.

Additionally, I conducted training and consultation activities with over 20 SMEs and agricultural innovators, helping them understand and apply open standards in their IoT solutions, improve certification readiness (ISO/CE), and integrate interoperable architectures into their products and services. Overall, the fellowship created a link between European standardisation efforts and regional implementation, ensuring that ICT standards for IoT and smart agriculture are accessible, inclusive, and impactful across both policy and business ecosystems.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Many SMEs in the region in Kosovo were previously unaware of these frameworks or how to integrate them into their systems. Through training sessions, workshops, and one-on-one consultations, I helped more than 20 SMEs understand how to design interoperable, standards-based solutions and prepare for ISO/CE certification. This work not only improved their technical readiness and competitiveness but also created stronger connections between local innovation ecosystems and EU standardisation initiatives, supporting the broader goal of SME inclusion in Europe's digital and green transition.

Impact on Society

My fellowship contributed to several important societal impacts in the fields of sustainability, digital inclusion, and innovation capacity across the Western Balkans. By promoting IoT standardisation in agriculture, my work supported the development of more efficient water-management systems, reducing waste and improving crop productivity — directly contributing to the EU Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 2: Zero Hunger, SDG 6: Clean Water, SDG 13: Climate Action).

Through cooperation with national authorities and regional business associations, I helped raise awareness among SMEs, farmers, and policymakers about the value of interoperable digital tools. This strengthened digital literacy, encouraged data-driven decision-making, and fostered trust in technology within the agricultural community.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

No, my activity targeted dissemination existing European and international standards on national level.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

My main recommendation is to increase awareness, training, and inclusion of regional experts and SMEs in the ongoing development and implementation of IoT and digital-agriculture standards. While frameworks such as ETSI SAREF4Agri and ISO/IEC 30141 are mature, their real-world adoption in the agricultural domain—especially across smaller EU states and the Western Balkans—remains limited.

Online references related to the fellowship work

📄 <https://www.fao.org/digital-villages-initiative/europe/news-and-articles/news-and-articles-detail/kosovo-s-digital-agriculture-programme-and-action-plan-2025-2028-formally-adopted-and-officially-presented/en>

Leading the development of ITU standards for IoT and Metaverse in smart cities and communities

Marios Angelopoulos

*Professor of Networked and Sensing Systems, Bournemouth University
United Kingdom*

Sector

Internet of Things (IoT)

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ITU-T Study Group 20 Internet of things (IoT) and smart cities and communities (SC&C)
FG-MV - Focus Group on metaverse

Role

Rapporteur of Question 5 “Study of emerging digital technologies, terminology and definitions” in ITU-T Study Group 20 “

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My work in ITU addresses the priorities of the call pertaining to smart cities and communities/ technologies and services for smart and efficient energy use, and citizen centric digital public services. The work is highly relevant to the European Commission’s strategy for Europe as the development of standards provisioning the use of crowdsourcing methodologies is aligned with one of the nine initiatives mentioned in a recent report by the European Commission DG Communications Networks, Content & Technology to lead the way is ‘empowering cities and communities across Europe’ through ‘better public services for citizens, better use of resources and less impact on the environment’. Furthermore, leading ITU-T Q5/20 which studies emerging technologies and definitions enables me to align work to European Commission’s initiatives, such as Digital Product Passports.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My StandICT fellowship supports my engagement and contribution to the International Telecommunications Union (ITU), one of the most prominent and impactful SDOs in the area of ICT with a global outreach to policy makers, Industry and Academia. In particular, the fellowship supports me in my role as Rapporteur of Question 5 “Study of emerging digital technologies, terminology and definitions” in ITU-T Study Group 20 “Internet of Things, smart cities and communities”. Currently SG20/Q5 has six active work items covering areas such as blockchain terms and definitions for IoT, digital transformation, and Digital Product Passports.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

ITU-T Q5/20 studies emerging technologies and active work items include topics of high-relevance to European market, such as Digital Product Passports. The development of international standards will help provide European SMEs, policy makers and regulators

with common references thus helping overcome market barriers such as technology fragmentation, thus promoting market growth.

Impact on Society

The work items of Question 5 of ITU-T Study Group 20 collectively support significant societal impact by advancing the integration of intelligent, sustainable, and transparent digital systems. The development of standards such as the Digital Product Passport for ICT goods (Y.DPP-ICT and YSTR.OS-DPP-ICT) promotes circular economy practices, enabling traceability, sustainability, and responsible consumption. Initiatives like Y.CIP enhance public safety through metaverse-based emergency response systems for chemical industrial parks, leveraging immersive technologies for disaster preparedness and risk management. Frameworks for distributed intelligent computing (YSTR.DIC) and embodied artificial intelligence (YSTR.EAI) contribute to the evolution of smart sustainable cities by enabling efficient resource utilization and human-centric automation. Meanwhile, the Hybrid AI-based Oral Assessment Platform (YSTR.AIOAP) reflects the application of ethical AI in education and skills evaluation. Together, these efforts foster safer, smarter, and more sustainable digital societies aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to the development of new standards. In the latest meeting, a new work item were established Y.DPP-ICT “Requirements and System Architecture of Digital Product Passport for ICT Goods” and STR.OS-DPP-ICT “A case study of an open-source Digital Product Passport system for ICT goods use case”.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

[StandICT.eu](https://www.standict.eu) fellowship has been proven critical in supporting my participating in ITU-T meetings. The continued support of my role as an expert directly supports EU presence in ITU; a presence that is already rather week. This has also been discussed in the context of ITU-COM (the European region of ITU). Also, The typical timescale for work items to be concluded in ITU is around two years (time period from the establishment of a work item until the publication of its outcome). This fellowship has been successful in establishing new work items in an areas that are highly relevant to the European strategic agenda. As such, continual support of this activity is suggested in order to allow for it successful fruition.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://www.itu.int/ITU-T/workprog/wp_search.aspx?sp=18&sg=20&q=5

Finalising QRNG standards employing quantum entanglement with secret validation for cryptography

Witold Jacak

University Professor at Wrocław University of Science and Technology

Chair of the Board of Directors of EITCI Institute

Coordinator of the EITCI Quantum Standards Group, European Information Technologies Certification Institute

Belgium

Sector

Quantum Technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

| EITCI QSG-QRNG

Role

Chair

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The action finalizes previous contributions to quantum cryptography standardisation in terms of its key enabling technology, i.e. quantum random numbers generation. Continued effort in QRNG standards including especially approaches based on entanglement schemes, with technical referencing of implementation techniques is expected to support uptake of the QRNG technology in general.

While the QKD technical standards are developed for several years and are now mature enough to provide device independent security (e.g. in efforts of the ETSI QKD-ISG Industry Specification Group), there are currently limited technical reference standards scopes for quantum randomness, despite the QRNG being a key enabler for QKD. The only two international QRNG standardisation initiatives both stemming from 2019 include ID Quantique's coordination of the efforts towards a dedicated WG establishment on the forum of the ITU-T, and the EITCI WG EQRNG-QSG WG that I chair.

New concepts and technical developments in quantum randomness generation and testing throughout the recent years will facilitate drafting of extended QRNG in-depth technical reference standards, beyond the scope of the currently limited QRNG standards inventory, compiling inputs from international SDOs' relevant WGs and domain experts, aiming at further consolidation of a high expertise level required for successfully supporting international efforts in quantum technology standardisation.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship supports standardisation efforts in quantum information processing and communication (QIPC) technologies towards facilitating their uptake as roadmapped in the EU Quantum Flagship program. It aims to advance international work on quantum randomness (QRNG) standardization, simultaneously supporting Europe's position on international SDOs/SSOs forum, leveraging on the EU's far-reaching quantum infrastructure projects.

These efforts are complementary with international standardisation actions. In Europe ETSI has established in 2008 the Industry Specification Group working on QKD, ETSI QKD-ISO (as outcome of SECOQC project), and on an international level quantum standards efforts take place in cybersecurity and networks WGs, mainly under JTC 1 of ISO/IEC. The CEN and CENELEC recently signed agreements with ISO and IEC through which common European and international standards are developed in parallel without duplication, emphasising European role in initiating several international quantum standards. Quantum standardisation is developed also in QISS of IEEE (P1913, P7130, P7131 WGs), ITU-T and ISA and NIST in the US. In 2018 the European QF Programme launched the Quantum Internet Alliance joining 12 research groups from 8 EU countries along with 20+ companies, workings towards breakthrough in quantum repeater technology enabling intermetropolitan exchange of entanglement that conditions practical quantum internet.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

With progress in quantum computation increasing investments are allocated at quantum technologies, including QKD and QIPC. Programs such as the Quantum Flagship in Europe have counterparts globally allocating billions of euros and dollars in R&D. SMEs play a crucial role in development of innovation and with QT it is no exception. Standards for basic quantum infrastructures such as quantum information encryption in future quantum networks can support innovation in quantum technology and accelerate its uptake by European SMEs. This is already happening among multiple startups in Europe, with a lot of their founders and/or key engineers engaging in the standardisation effort of the action with expert cooperation developing.

Impact on Society

The societal impact of the action is in supporting European's leading role in quantum technologies. Quantum engineering is expected to revolutionize industry on an unprecedented scale, surpassing technological revolutions witnessed so far. It is important for Europe and its citizens to be at the forefront of these developments as they will define economic and hence societal position of the EU in the future.

European leaders understand potential of quantum technologies and allocate adequate means to support research and development in this domain with programs such as the Quantum Flagship (QF) or the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI).

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. I have directly contributed to publication of two technical reference standards in protocols and implementations for advanced entanglement QRNG devices: RS-EITCI-EQRNG-PROTOCOL-STD and RS-EITCI-EQRNG-IMPLEMENTATION-STD.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The European Commission has recently launched the EuroQCI program implemented by all of the EU member states, targeted at building quantum terrestrial & satellite network as an infrastructure for quantum systems in the EU and for anticipated quantum computers. In recent years two important breakthroughs have been reported by Google (USA) and USTC (China) with the so called quantum supremacy of quantum processors (Sycamore implemented on superconducting Josephson junctions and Jiuzhang built on entangled photons), able to solve computational problems beyond the reach of classical computational power. The advent of quantum computers pronounces the need to develop quantum standards and especially so in quantum cryptography domain for fully quantum networks. The on-chip QRNG devices are important foundational elements on a path for quantum

Internet uptake that needs to be pursued in order to provide quantum security for the future of communication in terms of a fully secure communication infrastructure for quantum computing nodes.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://eitci.org/technology-certification/qsg/earng>

Building New Standardisation Working Group for Quantum Interconnect

Richard Pitwon

*CEO, Resolute Photonics UK Ltd
United Kingdom*

Sector

Quantum Technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEC TC86 WG11 - Quantum Optical Interconnect

Role

Convenor of IEC TC86 WG11 - Quantum Optical Interconnect

Chair of IEC TC86 SC86B - Fibre optic interconnecting devices and passive components

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The formation in 2024 of the ISO/IEC JTC3 on Quantum Technologies is providing the most far-reaching body for quantum standards development covering the full range of quantum technologies across the pillars of quantum communication, quantum computation and quantum sensing, metrology and imaging. However the scope of JTC3 explicitly excludes IEC TC86 fibre optics. This represents a huge gap in standardisation of the most mainstream aspects of quantum technologies, in particular quantum scalable networks for secure communication, photonic quantum computing and quantum sensing and imaging require a robust standards eco-system for fibre optic and photonic components. IEC TC86 WG11 fills this gap and provides a highly strategic opportunity for European organisations to mould the foundational standards in this field.

Europe currently leads the world in quantum science, however commercial realisation of that knowledge continues to be hindered by the fact that many companies that have the capabilities required for elements of the quantum interconnect supply chain do not frequently collaborate. Consequently, European developers must seek out bespoke solutions from a fragmented ecosystem or take advantage of more responsive offerings available outside Europe. While the industrial aspects of these challenges are being addressed by European collaborative R&D initiatives, it will be particularly critical for European companies to influence and develop international standardisation of quantum technologies.

To ensure that European industrial stakeholder needs are integrated into the standards development process, I have leveraged my extensive network to encourage active participation through European NCs. I have led as convenor, the newly formed IEC TC86 WG11 through its first year and expanded its membership to over 40 people. I have also prepared and submitted the first general and guidance standard for quantum grade connectors.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The main objective of this fellowship was to lead the newly formed IEC TC86 WG11 through its first year, continue to rapidly build up the membership of this WG primarily from Europe, and expedite a series of quantum interconnect standards from the membership.

I organised and chaired the first face to face meeting of IEC TC86 WG11 in September 2025 at the IEC General Meeting in New Delhi.

At the time of this final report I have grown the membership of this WG11 to 39 members of which 17 members (45%) are from Europe. While I have been successful in ensuring a strong European membership of this group, the total member number falls short of the original target of 75.

I completed the first draft of a general and guidance standard for quantum grade optical connectors, (IEC 6xxxx - FIBRE OPTIC INTERCONNECTING DEVICES AND PASSIVE COMPONENTS – QUANTUM FIBRE OPTIC CONNECTOR OPTICAL INTERFACES – Part 1: Quantum grade optical connector interfaces for single-mode non-dispersion shifted fibres – General and guidance).

I organised and chaired the NPL IoP Joint Symposium on Quantum Technologies⁵ on 14th and 15th October 2025 at NPL.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

I have built up the membership of this group, which at the time of the final report now has 39 members including 17 members from Europe, which includes some SMEs. The membership is therefore overwhelmingly European (45%). In particular through my fellowship I have consulted with many European quantum and photonic SMEs including Wave Photonics, Bay Photonics and Lumino to actively promote participation through BSI, which is a relatively easy process compared to other European NCs.

Impact on Society

European participation and influence in quantum standards groups will be critical to provide a boost across the European supply-chain enabling a larger European quantum market.

The potential benefits to society of quantum networks and quantum computers will be huge. Quantum safe networks will be required to send confidential data securely over appreciable distances and quantum computers will allow impossible world-scale simulations to be carried out in reasonable times.

Europe is already a world-leader in the scientific research and industrialisation of quantum technologies, especially with regards to quantum communication and quantum computation technologies. The key outcome of this fellowship was the successful establishment of IEC TC86 WG11 on Quantum Optical Interconnect as an active and growing Working Group. This new WG11 is strategically critical as its standards will strongly underpin quantum communication and networks, as well as contributing to all other quantum pillars.

By ensuring European SMEs participate actively in this new WG to apply Europe aligned positions on quantum technologies from ethical, industrial and academic angles, European influence on quantum standards will be strengthened and European society will be in a stronger position to establish a global competitive edge in this field.

These areas align well with strengths and expertise in European academic institutions and smaller start-up companies. Thus I have during this fellowship leveraged my extended network to increase involvement of the nascent European quantum industry, drawing primarily on UK, Swiss and EU entities for future support of and contributions to the new working group, thereby establishing strong European influence from the outset. I have successfully grown the membership to 39 members and I expect this to continue to grow rapidly now that we have started developing strategically critical new standards, in particular for quantum grade connectors.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

As part of this project I completed the first draft of a general and guidance standard for quantum grade optical connectors, (IEC 6xxxx - FIBRE OPTIC INTERCONNECTING DEVICES AND PASSIVE COMPONENTS – QUANTUM FIBRE OPTIC CONNECTOR OPTICAL INTERFACES

5 <https://www.npl.co.uk/events/npl-iop-joint-symposium-on-quantum-technologies-2025>

– Part 1: Quantum grade optical connector interfaces for single-mode non-dispersion shifted fibres – General and guidance).

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Although in this fellowship I have successfully guided the new WG11 through its first year, it is still a nascent group and as such is at its most vulnerable. It is critical to continue support for this group to ensure that European organisations continue to maintain a strong influence from its outset.

We have seen this effect from other newly formed WGs e.g. from Japan, where Japanese secretariat proposes the WG and maintains a very strong presence in those groups still. The same can be true of this group, but European StandIC.eu support should continue to ensure this.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:14:214778148600892:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:5229,25

3. Innovation for the Digital Single Market

ISO TC 307 Convenor WG3 Smart Contracts and its applications

Ismael Arribas
CEO, kunfud cero seis s.l.
Spain

Sector

Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO TC 307 Blockchain and Distributed ledger technologies WG3 Smart Contracts

Role

Convenor

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship supports my role as a convenor of ISO TCC307 WG3. The priority is to organise the appropriate ballots and meetings to allow the experts to discuss and reach a consensus based on the comments received for the projects in ISO TC 307 WG3. Another priority is to complete the norms with the attendance list and verify that all experts in the meeting were duly registered in the portal and authorised to participate in the meetings.

One of the main challenges of this work has been overcoming the cultural barriers and language differences encountered during this period, particularly through various meetings and ad hoc meetings for the three projects, which are ongoing in preparation for the final stage to publication.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship supports my work as a convenor of WG3 for Smart Contracts and its applications in ISO TC 307. Also, during these activities, I am also conducting actions with various liaisons in category A, including INATBA, OECD, EEA, and LACnet. However, the specific work of my fellowship is focused on WG3, supporting the project leaders and the other experts from national bodies, which currently comprise 43 participating countries and 20 observing countries in ISO TC 307.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Smart contracts are a fundamental enabler for developing with other technologies. In particular, the taxonomy and classification of smart contracts will contribute to understanding the scope within the Data Act and avoid confusion with some smart contracts that are not limited to the scope of the Data Act, thereby making it more comprehensive for the Digital Single Market and future strategy. The context of the EUDIC, EBSI, and other advancements for smart communities will gain a clear perspective with the technical specification TS 18126 (Taxonomy and classification for smart contracts).

In addition, the Sustainable Development Goals, which many projects of SMEs and other European societies are pursuing, will have guidance on how smart contracts are contributing

to achieve the SDGs; this will be a Publicly Available Specification (PAS) 24874 (Guidance on the use of smart contracts in contributing to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)).

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

The activities I have achieved were in relation to three projects that will lead to new standards that were under development in ISO TC 307 WG3 for Smart Contracts and its applications.

The following three projects are currently in the final stage before publication.

- ▶ ISO/CD TS 18126 (Taxonomy and classification for smart contracts)
- ▶ ISO/CD PAS 24874 (Guidance on the use of smart contracts in contributing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs))
- ▶ ISO/DTR 25145 (Overview of DLT-based collections and collections management)

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The above-mentioned three projects are in the final stage. More than 200 editorial comments were corrected and harmonised. I support the project leaders in accommodating the formatting requirements for the next balloting period. Hence, they are in the process of the final revision by the ISO/CS for approval to move to the next stage before publication.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/6266604.html>

Standards development in blockchain and DLT and finance that contribute to Sustainability

Caroline Thomas

*Independent expert in global financial services, compliance and regulatory environments.
Greece*

Sector

Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and DLT Technologies - WG6 Use Cases
ISO/TC322 Sustainable Finance - WG2 Terminology
ISO/TC68 ISO/TC 68 Financial Services - JWG1 Digital Currencies

Role

Convenor of ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and DLT Technologies - WG6 Use Cases

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This supports the preparation of two plenaries, including: ISO/TC 322 October 2025 and ISO/TC 307 Plenary organised in November 2025. Also, I support the ongoing work in ISO/TC 68 and JWG1.

This work considers the inter-dependencies between ESG funding and funding instruments (eg: carbon markets), financial transparency products (eg: carbon credits) and DLT/blockchain technologies that provide transparency & trust in Sustainability records.

Therefore stakeholders across the Sustainability spectrum can access a baseline of common standards, that underpin and inform their technical, financial, business, legal and consumer decisions.

This standardisation work aims to include the capabilities of how Blockchain/DLT solutions can address and verify the current Environmental emergencies and apply the rapid evolution of new digital, crypto and tokenised forms of finance.

Moreover, the global priority of standards to enable Sustainable Growth. This objective supports the development of international standards for DLT/blockchain technologies to ensure transparency in sustainable financing. This new work is necessary due to urgent shift in international technology advances and regional regulations including AI, tokenisation & crypto-currencies, that may provide potential challenges to European laws, ethics and societies.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

As Convenor of ISO/TC 307 WG6, I am contributing to development of the following ICT standards:

- ▶ At ISO/TC 307 WG6 Use cases including ISO/ TR WD 24878 New and emerging DLT/Blockchain Use Cases⁶ and White Papers on the Use Case Methodologies.
- ▶ At ISO/TC 322 Sustainable Finance as a member of this group and liaison from TC 307, I am

⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/88315.html?browse=tc>

contributing to ISO/WD TS 32219 Sustainable Finance — Terminology for impact, risk and related information technology⁷.

- ▶ ISO/TC 68 Financial Services as a member of this group and liaison from TC 307, I am contributing to: ISO/AWI 24982 Digital currencies — Vocabulary⁸.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society) Impact on Society

This new work is necessary to address the urgent shift in international technology advances, such as AI, tokenisation and crypto-currencies, that may provide potential challenges to European laws, ethics and societies. Standards can provide trust in an environment of AI-generated fake news.

For example, the work on ISO/AWI 24982 Digital currencies — Vocabulary helps define a common international language for business and societies, to create an interoperable financial system in digital currencies. Or the work on — ISO/WD TS 32219 Sustainable Finance — Terminology helps define a common international language for business and societies, across these regulations and business reporting.

This Standards work in blockchain and DLT can help inform businesses, SMEs and societies by providing insights in guidelines to enable adoption, trust and scale in their businesses and networks.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I have contributed to several new standardisation projects as listed above.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

There are varying degrees of maturity. While sustainability has been a priority scanning decades of activity before and since the 1st COP in 1995, the technical capabilities and financial markets are very dynamic. This new work is necessary to address the urgent shift in international technology advances and regional regulations including AI, tokenisation and crypto-currencies, that may provide potential challenges to European laws, ethics and societies.

The recommendation for continuation of action is based on the three related standards in development, which are all in the early stages of the ISO drafting process, which extends to a two to three year timeframe.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/6266604.html

 www.iso.org/committee/7203746.html

 www.iso.org/committee/49650.html

⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77785.html?browse=tc>

⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/88729.html>

Contribution to Joint ISO/TC 307 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 JWG4

Ljupcho Antovski

*Professor of Software Engineering, Faculty of Computer Science and Engineering
Macedonia*

Sector

Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

Joint ISO/TC 307 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 Working Group 4: Security, privacy and identity for Blockchain and DLT

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Standardisation in the field of Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies is imperative to promote interoperability, security, and innovation across European markets. The rapid evolution of these technologies has led to a fragmented landscape of standards globally. This fragmentation presents challenges such as hindered cross-border data flow and increased compliance burdens on European businesses. My activity aims to address these critical gaps by actively participating in the creation of comprehensive, internationally recognized standards.

My engagement in the Joint ISO/TC 307 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG directly supports this action. By actively participating in WG, I am bolstering Europe's representation and influence in shaping global standards in this transformative domain.

From a European perspective, this activity is pivotal. Europe seeks to not only embrace but lead in the adoption and implementation of Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies. By participating in the development of standards, we ensure that Europe's interests, values, and priorities are ingrained in the foundation of these technologies. This is paramount for bolstering Europe's digital sovereignty, fostering innovation, and ensuring that European businesses remain competitive on the global stage.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The primary objective of this proposal is to actively engage in and contribute to the Joint ISO/TC 307 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 Working Group 4 projects, including:

- ▷ ISO/WD 24876.2 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies — Privacy protection when involving trust anchors in DLT-based identity management.
- ▷ ISO/WD 25126.4 Information security controls based on ISO/IEC 27002 for distributed ledger services.
- ▷ ISO/AWI 24946 - Requirements and guidance for improving, preserving, and assessing the privacy capability of DLT systems.

My aim is to lend my expertise to the standardisation efforts, thereby advancing Europe's leadership and ensuring the development of robust, internationally recognised standards. The

activities align seamlessly with the strategic priorities outlined in The European Commission Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation (EC RP).

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society) Impact on Society

The core social impact of my work is safeguarding European interests, values, and citizen rights in the foundational rules that will govern emerging digital technologies worldwide. The key areas of social Impact included: protecting privacy and security for citizens, promoting European digital sovereignty, promote interoperability, allowing for smoother cross-border data flow and services, foster innovation by creating a stable and predictable technical environment.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. I am contributing to several new ISO blockchain and LTD standardisation projects, as listed above.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The area of blockchain and DLT is evolving and continuous participation of European experts is advisable in order to protect the European interests and stay on top of the developments in this area. More specifically, the stages of the current projects are:

- ▶ ISO/WD 24876.2 20.60 Close of comment period
- ▶ ISO/WD 25126.4 20.20 Working draft (WD) study initiated

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/6266604.html

Reliable, Automated Generation of EN16931 Code List Artefacts for European e-Invoicing

Svante Schubert

Freelancer

Germany

Sector

E-Invoicing

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN TC 434 Technical Committee For Electronic Invoicing Standards

CEN TC 434 WG1 Core semantic data model

CEN TC 434 WG3 Syntax bindings

CEN TC 434 WG5 Extension methodology

OASIS OpenDocument Format (ODF) TC

Role

Member and editor in CEN TC 434

Chair of OASIS OpenDocument Format (ODF) TC

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

A key goal of my work is to advance the digital transformation of standardisation itself. While digital processes are already common in business and administration, most standards are still developed using traditional, text-based methods with a high degree of manual effort. I aim to make standards digital, machine-readable, and easier to maintain, supported by tools that enable automated versioning, validation, and quality assurance.

I also strongly promote the use and evolution of Open Standards. Open and freely available standards encourage broader participation, faster development cycles, and more thorough expert review across the European and international community.

With the fellowship, I can expand my ongoing work on the European e-invoicing standard EN16931, turning voluntary contributions into focused development. The goal is to bridge the gap between theoretical standard specifications and practical implementation through automation and open-source collaboration.

Ultimately, this effort contributes to greater efficiency, transparency, and digital sovereignty within Europe's standardisation ecosystem — ensuring that the standards themselves become as modern and interoperable as the digital solutions they enable.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship contributes to the ICT standards landscape by improving the quality, transparency, and sustainability of the artefacts that underpin the European e-invoice standard EN16931. Code lists are a critical part of semantic interoperability, ensuring that terms such as currencies, countries, VAT categories, and identifiers are used consistently across Europe. By automating the generation of these artefacts from a single authoritative source, the project removes duplication, reduces errors, and ensures reliable updates for both European and international stakeholders.

The contribution is twofold:

- ▶ Strengthening European interoperability: The outputs support cross-border e-invoicing as mandated by Directive 2014/55/EU, ensuring all Member States and sectors can rely on consistent artefacts for legal compliance and interoperability.
- ▶ Supporting international alignment: By producing artefacts that are synchronised with OASISUBL and UN/CEFACT CII, the project bridges European requirements with global e-business standards, reinforcing Europe's leadership role.

In addition, the work provides tooling under a European FOSS license (EUPL), enabling long-term reuse, extension, and integration by CEN/TC 434, CEN/TC 440, OASIS UBL TC, UN/CEFACT, and national initiatives such as XRechnung or Factur-X/ZUGFeRD. The ICT Standards addressed cover:

- ▶ EN 16931 – Semantic data model of the core elements of an electronic invoice
- ▶ OASIS Genericcode – Code list representation format
- ▶ ISO/IEC 19845 (UBL) – Universal Business Language
- ▶ UN/CEFACT CII – Cross Industry Invoice
- ▶ ISO 4217 – Currency codes
- ▶ ISO 3166 – Country codes
- ▶ ISO 639 – Language codes
- ▶ IANA Media Types – Internet media type registry
- ▶ UN/ECE Recommendations & UN/EDIFACT – Trade, transport, and identifier code lists

By delivering higher-quality artefacts and open automation, the project strengthens both European digital sovereignty and Europe's global influence in ICT standardisation.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

My contribution has a direct positive impact on European SMEs by simplifying the implementation of the EN16931 e-invoicing standard. The automated generation of high-quality code list artefacts removes inconsistencies and reduces technical complexity, allowing SMEs to integrate compliant e-invoicing into their business software more easily and at lower cost. This helps smaller companies meet public procurement and cross-border trade requirements without relying on expensive proprietary tools. By publishing the tooling under a European FOSS license, SMEs gain free access to transparent, reliable, and reusable resources that strengthen their competitiveness and participation in the Digital Single Market.

Impact on Society

My work supports several key societal impacts aligned with Europe's digital and sustainability goals. By improving the quality and automation of EN16931 e-invoicing artefacts, it strengthens the Digital Single Market and enables more efficient, transparent, and paperless business processes across Europe. This directly contributes to administrative simplification, environmental sustainability, and cost reduction—especially for SMEs and public administrations.

Through the use of open-source tools and open standards, my work also promotes digital sovereignty, ensuring that Europe's core interoperability infrastructure remains transparent, accessible, and under European control. By fostering collaboration between public and private actors, the project helps create a more inclusive and resilient digital ecosystem that benefits businesses, citizens, and administrations alike.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. My project directly supports the revision of the existing European e-invoicing standard EN16931. The work focuses on improving the quality and maintainability of its supporting artefacts through automation and open-source tooling. By developing a process to automatically generate and validate all code list artefacts (spreadsheets and OASIS Genericcode XML) from a single authoritative source, the project introduces a sustainable approach that can be adopted in the upcoming EN16931 revision cycle.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The standard EN16931 and its supporting artefacts have reached a good level of maturity, but continued work is essential to ensure their quality, maintainability, and alignment with real-world implementations. I recommend a continuation of action, focused on improving the digitalisation of the standardisation process itself.

Future work should include automated generation and validation of artefacts (e.g., code lists and syntax bindings), better coordination between CEN, OASIS, and UN/CEFACT, and the adoption of agile, iterative review cycles rather than waterfall-style revisions. This will reduce errors, accelerate updates, and support open, transparent collaboration. Sustained action will ensure that EN16931 remains accurate, interoperable, and adaptable to future EU digital and regulatory requirements.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/ords/f?p=205:7:::FSP_ORG_ID:1883209&cs=14DD1206F34C582059B364D80C56C406D

Project Leader for “Digital Currencies - Vocabulary” in ISO TC68

Christian Grafenauer

*Consumer Representative, DIN Verbraucherrat e.V.
Germany*

Sector

FinTech & RegTech Standardisation

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

| ISO/TC 68/JWG 1 – Digital Currencies: Vocabulary

Role

Project leader

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The project addresses the lack of a harmonised vocabulary for digital currencies, which creates legal uncertainty, interoperability issues, and confusion across finance, law, and technology. Key terms like digital token or wallet are defined inconsistently by ISO, ECB, EBA, and MiCA, undermining regulatory enforcement and preventing standards from supporting presumption of conformity under EU law.

The priority is to align terminology with the EU Digital Finance Strategy, MiCA, DORA, and the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation. A coherent vocabulary supports regulatory clarity, cross-border financial services, and initiatives like EBSI, while reinforcing Europe’s leadership in trustworthy digital infrastructures.

The main challenge is balancing precision, usability, and consensus. Terms must be detailed enough to anchor legislation yet practical for SMEs, regulators, and developers. Through bi-weekly meetings, strong European leadership, and expert engagement, the project is building a consensus-driven vocabulary that bridges legal, financial, and technical domains.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The project strengthens the ICT standards landscape by providing a harmonised vocabulary for digital currencies, ensuring clarity and interoperability across finance, law, and technology. By consolidating fragmented terminology, it creates a foundation for consistent regulation, compliance, and technical implementation in Europe and globally.

It directly contributes to ISO/AWI 24982 “Digital Currencies — Vocabulary”, developed within ISO/TC 68/JWG 1 (Financial Services and Blockchain/DLT), and feeds into European work under CEN-CLC/JTC 19/WG3. This ensures alignment with EU priorities while influencing global standardisation. The vocabulary also complements related standards such as ISO 20022 (financial messaging) and the broader ISO/TC 307 blockchain standards.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

For SMEs, a harmonised digital currency vocabulary reduces compliance costs and uncertainty when navigating regulations like MiCA and DORA. It lowers barriers to entry by providing a

shared reference for financial, legal, and technical terms, enabling smaller companies and fintechs to innovate confidently and scale solutions across the Digital Single Market.

Impact on Society

By developing a harmonised vocabulary for digital currencies, it strengthens legal certainty and consumer protection, allowing citizens and businesses to engage confidently with technologies such as CBDCs, stablecoins, and tokenised assets. Clear definitions reduce misunderstanding and misinformation, supporting informed participation in digital markets.

It also enhances trust in digital public infrastructures by enabling regulators, financial institutions, and public administrations to use a shared language. This improves transparency in policymaking and aligns digital finance with Europe's values of privacy, fairness, and accountability.

Finally, today's Web3 ecosystem and traditional financial system speak fundamentally different languages, limiting cooperation and interoperability. This project builds the common language needed for both ecosystems to grow together and operate seamlessly, fostering a unified, transparent, and future-ready European digital economy.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I lead the standard project; ISO/AWI 24982 - Digital currencies — Vocabulary.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I recommend the continuation of the current action, as the work on the Digital Currencies — Vocabulary standard is progressing steadily but remains at a crucial stage. The initial draft of around 200 terms has been consolidated, yet further refinement, alignment with EU regulatory frameworks (MiCA, DORA), and consensus-building among experts are still required. Continued support will ensure that Europe maintains a strong leadership role in shaping global terminology for digital currencies. The next phase should focus on expanding stakeholder engagement, improving cross-references with related standards (ISO 20022, TC 307 outputs), and integrating feedback from financial institutions and regulators. Sustained participation is essential to achieve a harmonised, authoritative vocabulary that can serve as a foundation

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/49650.html>

JTC1 CG2 - Strategic Coordination Group on Metaverse

Torbjörn Lahrin
*Independent Expert, i Hajstorp AB
Sweden*

Sector

Web 4.0 and virtual worlds

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1 CG2 - Strategic Coordination Group on Metaverse

Role

Convenor of ISO/IEC JTC1/CG2 – Strategic Coordination Group on Metaverse

Co-convenor JWG between JTC and SyC Smart Cities on Urban Digital Twins and City Information Modelling

Convenor of ISO/IEC SC41/AG21. Advisory and Sectorial Liaison Group

Convenor of W3C Nordic Chapter Smart City / Web Of Things Community Group.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Metaverse is an emerging technology and paradigm shift for the whole society. A great many standardisation bodies have set out to define what Metaverse is and how it should be interpreted, shaped and standardised. Many of these efforts are very good, but they are not synchronised.

JTC1 is having a leading role in ICT standardization. Thus, many of the core standards needed for Metaverse is and will be developed within JTC1 and the Sub Committees of JTC1. JTC1 also needs to reach out to the other standardisation organisations addressing Metaverse standardisation to make sure that all good efforts are taken into consideration and to avoid gaps in the perception and related future work.

The work of CG2 is to strategically coordinate the efforts and standardisation regarding Metaverse within JTC1., which includes identification of gaps, priorities and challenges as well as help other JTC1 sub-committees to find means to solve them. A vital part of the work is to establish good relations to those other organisations, outside JTC1, engaged in Metaverse standardisation. The strategic work also address the relationship between Metaverse and CitiVerse.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

I supported drafting the [StandICT.eu](https://standict.eu) produced “Standardisation Landscape for CitiVerse⁹”. This report lists around 350 standards, technical reports and technical specifications that might need to be considered when creating standards for CitiVerse. A majority of these are also involved in the making of standards for Metaverse.

It is not doable to list all these standards here, but the core work of CG2 is to coordinate all these standards, and to address gaps where new standards will be needed. Thus this project is contributing to a wide range of the ICT Standards landscape.

9 <https://standict.eu/news/landscape-citiverse-standards>

The members of CG2 are primary the chairs of the SC:s within JTC1. Thus, the primary focus for CG2 is the related standards in the Sub Committees of JTC1. However, CG2 also reach out to acknowledge and coordinate valuable standards, deliverables and work in other organizations like ITU-T, W3C, IEEE and others.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Investing in Metaverse and CitiVerse is today rather challenging. All technologies for creating Metaverse, CitiVerse and underlying Local Digital Twins have strengths and weaknesses. Such investments are therefore associated with a rather high degrade of uncertainty. Still, the SME:s and European societies must invest already now in these technologies to have a chance to be “on the train” and ahead in the competition. Also for implementing various parts of CitiVerse related to EU calls. However, this come with a large risk investing in the “wrong” direction with technique and methods that will not be long lasting.

Because of this European SMEs and societies will benefit from the creation and coordination of standards for Metaverse. They will also benefit from gaining knowledge about the international standardization, as such knowledge will help SME:s and societies of Europe to navigate and to invest in “right” directions with long term safer investments.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Not directly, as this fellowship supported by role as a convener of ISO/IEC JTC1/CG2 with the central aim to identify priorities and gaps for future standards in Metaverse as to liaise with other sub-committees.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The coordination of Metaverse standardization within JTC1 has just begun. There is a need for many more details and continued work on coordination activities and JWG:s between SC:s within JTC1. The attached overview of standards needed for Metaverse and committees involved clearly show how complex this coordination will be, raising the very urgent and important need for further coordination.

It should be noted that there is an ongoing discussion between ISO (TMB) and IEC (SMB) about eventually forming a new joint system committee between ISO and IEC on Metaverse. However, even if this becomes a reality such joint committee will need to cooperate very closely with JTC1 for the creation of needed standard. Thus, such new joint committee will most likely place even stronger demands on the internal coordination of Metaverse within JTC1.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/45020.html

Integrating Civerse and Local Digital Twins via Data Spaces

Antonio Jara

CSO, HOPU

Spain

Sector

Web 4.0 and virtual worlds

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ETSI ISG CIM & TC Data
ITU-T Civerse/VWGs
UNE/ISO CT73
Living-in.eu /OASC MIM8

Role

Co-Chair Living-in.eu / OASC MIM8

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The sectors of Digital Twins, Virtual Worlds/Civerse, IoT and Data Spaces are fragmented, especially the uneven uptake of NGSI-LD, Smart Data Models/SAREF and governance models creates a barrier for cross-domain interoperability in cities. Therefore, I focus on harmonising these layers within ITU-T Civerse and EU Local Digital Twin (LDT) Toolbox¹⁰. I also contribute to aligning LDT and Data Space governance with UNE 0087:2025 and the Gaia-X Trust Framework to operationalise sovereignty, compliance and automated conformance. Moreover, I contribute to mapping LDT/MIM8, NGSI-LD, SIMPL and Civerse deliverables to speed deployment and avoid duplicate or conflicting specs.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

I contribute to several different technical committees having a different impact to the standards landscape:

- ▶ ETSI ISG CIM / TC Data: contributions to the new Group Report “Using NGSI-LD for Local Digital Twins” (WKI 73752); weekly rapporteur meetings and a CIM#30 briefing ensure the LDT Toolbox’s NGSI-LD profiles and lifecycle patterns are captured.
- ▶ Living-in.EU / OASC – MIM8 (LDT): leadership and fortnightly contributions to define the LDT MIM (capabilities, requirements, mechanisms, conformance).
- ▶ ITU-T Civerse / Virtual Worlds: regular WG participation; inputs on LDT/Civerse alignment and a white-paper contribution (Emerging Tech Track—Global Digital Civerse Framework, author list includes Antonio Jara).
- ▶ UNE/ISO CT73 (Data Spaces): participation in GT2 Interoperability; first CTN73 document released with Toolbox “Data Space Ready” alignment.

In this sense, the referenced standards/specifications are the following: NGSI-LD & Smart Data Models/SAREF; MIM8; UNE 0087:2025; Gaia-X Trust Framework; IDSA Rulebook; ITU-T Y.4505 structure.

¹⁰ <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/ldttoolbox>

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Libelium is a SME and it has directly contribute to Libelium and other SMEs working on Data Spaces, Digital Twins and Citiverse by lowering entry costs via reusable NGSI-LD/MIM8 profiles and Toolbox components; reduced lock-in and faster integrations, and making easier the market access to Data Space Ready patterns (CT73/UNE) and Gaia-X alignment for trustworthy exchange.

Impact on Society

I see a bit different societal impact of each target project:

- ▷ Interoperable public services and vendor-neutral procurement via NGSI-LD/MIM8 profiles.
- ▷ Trustworthy data sharing for cities/SMEs through UNE 0087 an Gaia-X trust mechanisms.
- ▷ Inclusive urban innovation under the Citiverse initiative (human-centred, open, safe).

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to creating two new standards: ETSI ISG CIM GR “Using NGSI-LD for LDTs” (WKI 73752) and MIM8 (Local Digital Twins) within Living-in.eu/OASC

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I plan to apply for further fellowships within StandICT.eu2029 to continue working with the ETSI–MIM8–Citiverse mapping annex with conformance profiles (test hooks) for APIs, semantics and lifecycle that can be relevant for the EDIC of LDT and Citiverse, and the EU Local Digital Twin Toolbox. I also aim to establish joint liaisons (ETSI–OASC–ITU) to avoid duplication; run Toolbox-backed plug-tests with SMEs to promote its adoption and best-practices.

Finally, now the three priorities are establishing (i) NGSI-LD profiles for LDT orchestration; (ii) MIM8 conformance and certification path; (iii) Data-Space-Ready patterns (Gaia-X/UNE 0087) embedded in LDT deployments.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.itu.int/metaverse/wp-content/uploads/2025/11/DRAFT-Global-Digital-Citiverse-Framework.pdf

 <https://living-in.eu/groups/commitments>

4. Sustainable growth

Tokenisation Standards for Sustainable Assets Management

Limara Haque

COO, Kron World S.L.

United Kingdom

Sector

Circular Economy including Digital Product Passport

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies WG8 – Tokenization of Assets

CEN-CENELEC JTC 24 – Digital Product Passport (DPP) and Circular Data Flows

ISO/TC 154 – Processes, data models, and interoperability for electronic business

CEN-CENELEC JTC 19 WG2 – Environmental Sustainability and Blockchain

INATBA – Sustainability & Social Impact Working Group (Chair, 2025)

CIRPASS2 – Technical alignment for DPP architecture

AIOTI – DPP and Tokenisation Initiatives (in application)

Role

Member

Chair of INATBA – Sustainability & Social Impact Working Group

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship directly addressed three key challenges in the emerging landscape of asset tokenisation and sustainable digital infrastructure:

- ▶ **Standardisation Gaps for Tokenised Real-World Assets (RWAs):** While NFT and tokenisation technologies are maturing, they lack a unified, standards-based framework to represent physical assets in a verifiable, interoperable, and ESG-aligned manner. Under my leadership of ISO/TC 307 WG8 PWI 25315, I initiated the foundational work for a multi-part international standard, filling this global void.
- ▶ **Alignment with EU Sustainability Priorities (DPP, Green Deal, SME Digitalisation):** Europe urgently needs trusted digital representations of assets that support the Digital Product Passport (DPP), traceability, and circularity goals. This project ensured the standardisation approach integrates EU policy objectives across sectors, environment, digitalisation, and compliance, addressing regulatory gaps between innovation and enforcement.
- ▶ **Fragmentation Across SDOs and Lack of Cross-Policy Coherence:** A major challenge is the siloed approach between global and European standards bodies (ISO, CEN/CENELEC, UNECE, etc.). During the fellowship, I worked as a liaison and participant across multiple SDOs (TC307, JTC24, ISO/TC 154, CIRPASS2, AIOTI, INATBA) to foster cross-SDO coherence and prepare harmonised technical foundations that are future-proof and policy-aligned.

Through these efforts, the project not only met but anticipated market and regulatory needs, laying the groundwork for Europe to lead in sustainable, standards-driven tokenisation infrastructure

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This funded activity made a direct and strategic contribution to the ICT standards landscape by advancing a multi-part international standard on the tokenisation of asset classes under ISO/TC 307 WG8 (PWI 25315). The work initiated the architectural and governance design required to enable trusted digital representations of real-world assets (RWAs), including integration with the Digital Product Passport (DPP) and other sustainability-linked lifecycle infrastructures.

The project has strengthened the role of blockchain and DLT technologies in verifiable data systems by embedding them within globally accepted and European-aligned standards. It also ensured the intersection of tokenisation, governance, ESG compliance, and traceability were addressed in a modular, scalable way.

The involved ICT Standards include:

- ▶ ISO/TC 307 – Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies
 - ▶ PWI 25315 (led by me) – Tokenisation of Multi-Asset Classes
 - ▶ ISO 22739 – Vocabulary for DLT
 - ▶ ISO/TR 23455 – Smart contracts
 - ▶ ISO/TS 23635 – Governance of DLT systems
- ▶ CEN-CENELEC JTC 24 – Standards for Digital Product Passports and circular data systems
- ▶ ISO/TC 154 – Data interoperability and digital information flows
- ▶ UNECE & ISO 25534-1 – Joint foundational standard for global DPP systems
- ▶ Ethereum ERC-721 and ERC-1155 – Referenced for structuring token lifecycle logic

In parallel, the project engaged with the CIRPASS2 project and INATBA association, embedding ethical, technical, and regulatory considerations into the evolving standards fabric. Through active liaison roles and cross-SDO collaboration, this work ensures ICT standards evolve in a harmonised, secure, and sustainability-ready manner.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

My contribution directly supports European SMEs by lowering the barriers to adoption of trusted digital tools for sustainability, traceability, and compliance. Through the standardisation of tokenisation frameworks (ISO PWI 25315), SMEs can more easily issue verifiable digital representations of their products and services, aligned with EU regulations such as the Digital Product Passport (DPP), CSRD, ESPR, and MiCA.

This enables SMEs to participate in data-driven value chains, prove ESG performance, access impact finance, and engage with global supply networks, without relying on costly proprietary platforms. The work promotes interoperability, inclusion, and compliance-by-design, giving SMEs a scalable way to enter the digital economy while staying aligned with European values of fair access, innovation, and transparency.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contributed to developing a new ISO standard: PWI 25315 – Tokenisation of Multi-Asset Classes.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The standardisation of tokenisation frameworks must continue as a strategic priority, particularly in light of Europe's goals around Digital Product Passports (DPPs), ESG accountability, Green Deal implementation, and digital sovereignty. My current work under ISO/TC 307 WG8, specifically on the multi-part standard PWI 25315 and the new standard on

Tokenisation Methods in Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs), directly supports this.

I strongly recommend continuation of this work to:

- ▶ Advance the modularisation of PWI 25315 so that real-world asset (RWA) tokenisation is supported across sectors (e.g. finance, environmental assets, supply chains).
- ▶ Ensure the DLT Methodology standard (currently under ballot) progresses with European oversight, embedding values of openness, transparency, and governance-neutrality while addressing interoperability challenges between public, permissioned, and private DLTs.
- ▶ Align token standards with parallel developments in DPP infrastructure (CEN-CENELEC JTC24) and AIOTI, especially for machine-readable ESG data and verifiable claims.
- ▶ Protect European influence and leadership in global forums where tokenisation is rapidly becoming geopolitically sensitive.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/6266604.html

Information Management in Construction

Marzia Bolpagni

Associate Director, Digital Engineering & Building Information Modelling, Mace
Italy

Sector

Construction building information modelling

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/TC 442 Building Information Modelling (BIM)
ISO/TC59/SC13 Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM)

Role

Co-Chair of CEN/TC 442 Building Information Modelling (BIM) WG2 Exchange Information Project Group 1 on Level of Information need

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

As recognised by CEN, the construction sector is one of Europe's biggest industries, representing about 9% of the EU's GDP and 50.5% of Gross fixed Capital formation. It uses about 50% of the raw materials taken from the earth and generates about 40% of all greenhouse gas emissions in Europe. It employs more than 18 million EU citizens and it is estimated that 26 million workers in the EU depend, in one way or another, on the construction sector. However, it is one of the less digitalised sectors. For this reason, CEN/TC 442 is leading the publication of standards on digital construction, also referred as "building information modelling" BIM.

My fellowship supported the revision of three key standards on Building Information Modelling (BIM) at ISO under Vienna Agreement for the definition of information management processes. I also have been a role model for other young women in starting or continuing a career on ICT standardization for construction, where women are still less than 10%.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My application is contributing to the development of the following ICT standards: prEN ISO 19650 rev Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) — Information management using building information modelling

- Part 1: Concepts and principles
- Part 2: Information management process
- Part 3: Implementation of the information management process

BIM is a recognised topic of ICT standards landscape by the European Commission (see Rolling Plan for ICT standardisation- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH- Construction - building information modelling).

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The EU stakeholders will benefit from using a consistent process in projects to avoid waste of efforts. European SMEs will reduce time in creating their own processes and specification as they can use something already available in the industry internationally, as the standards I contributed to are developed at CEN and ISO levels. In this way, they will be able to work across different countries, projects, and clients.

Furthermore, European private and public clients will more easily be able to identify who is responsible for information management in their organisation and to set requirements in a digital way for transparent and more effective processes. The EU supply chain will be facilitated in producing better quality information thanks to software applications that follow standardised procedures included in ISO 19650 standards during the entire project lifecycle.

Impact on Society

While the construction sector is a key driver of the overall economy, it faces numerous challenges relating to, inter alia, competitiveness, labor shortage, resource efficiency and especially productivity. Digitalisation in construction is increasingly recognised as a game changer, which could contribute significantly to sustainable development within the European Green Deal and the "Europe fit for digital age" priorities. My work dealt with BIM that is seen by the European Commission as the main solution to digitalization of the construction ecosystem, for all phases of the asset lifecycle: procurement, design, construction (including assembly), operation and maintenance

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, in my leadership role within CEN/TC 442 WG2 I have contributed to developing new standards; prCEN ISO/TS 7817-2 (WI=00442057) and prEN ISO 7817-3 (WI=00442058).

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

It is suggested to continue working on the work items prEN ISO 19650-1 rev (WI=00442066), prEN ISO 19650-2 rev (WI=00442067) and prEN ISO 19650-3 rev (WI=00442068) by finalising the text for enquiry stage.

Online references related to the fellowship work

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/ords/f?p=205:7:::FSP_ORG_ID:1991542&cs=1CA359938D00DB1596780EE853DC82209

Contribute to PWI Common Data Environment (CDE) solution and workflow - Application framework

Pierre-François Jullien

Founder and Consultant, Atalane
France

Sector

Construction building information modelling

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN TC 442/WG 3 Information Delivery Specification
CEN TC 442/WG 2
AFNOR CN PPBIM/GE 2

Role

Convenor of AFNOR CN PPBIM/GE 2 and member in the other groups

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

To exchange information in a collaborative way, common data environments (CDE) are required. CDEs host in a unique place all the information related to a project: they enable users to share and update their project information in a collaborative way: 3D models, thermal or acoustic calculation results, life cycle assessments etc. There does not exist a standardized framework for CDEs. So partners usually exchange documents (PDFs, proprietary or IFC (ISO 16739-1) 3D models, ...) through email, with additional information in plain text in the email.

To perform this current exchange process, one needs to extract the files from one CDE, send them via email and then the receiving partner will have to load the files in its own CDE, and to reenter informations. Such a process is cumbersome and error prone. It is also a significant barrier to the digitization of SMEs. CDEs are currently useful to share information within a company; they are much less useful to share information between companies. As a consequence, only large companies use CDEs and SMEs don't use such tools.

The lack of a standardized framework also prevents the development of light solutions, focused on the user interface and that could interact with any CDE compliant with the standardized framework. Such solutions would allow an SME to keep the same user interface whatever CDE is chosen on a project and to minimize training costs.

This Preliminary Work Item aims at defining a framework for CDEs that will improve the flow of information. This framework will guide suppliers providing solutions to the market based on asset requirements - thus raising efficiency in information management. It will enable a seamless exchange of information and minimize the low value and error prone human tasks.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This project aims to develop standardized CDE APIs, that will support the process and functionalities defined by EN ISO 19650. The other standards it is dealing with are the EN ISO 7817 series and CEN TR 18093.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The European construction sector (including the process of design) is mainly made up of SMEs and suffers from a strong segmentation. Such a fragmentation has deep consequences regarding the digitization of the construction industry: unlike the aeronautics or automotive industries, there aren't a few major leaders able to impose a collaborative platform on all project participants (Airbus or Boeing do this). CDEs are a tool for implementing collaborative processes, but the absence of a standardized framework is preventing their widespread use. This project aims at developing a CDE framework that could help overcome the difficulties generated by the fragmentation of this sector.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, this fellowship focuses on developing a new standard for CDE APIs.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

This project is in preliminary stage (PWI), and its scope needs to be refined before taking any further action. Once activated, we will need from 24 to 36 months to finalize it.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2051463&cs=160D46F8CC9FE24E668878A098D1EB4DC

Support of JPEG Calls for Proposals responses on Objectives Quality Assessment Evaluation

Antonio Pinheiro

*Professor, U.B.I. - Universidade da Beira Interior & Instituto de Telecomunicações
Portugal*

Sector

Digitisation of European Industry

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29 Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypermedia information WG 1 JPEG Coding of digital representations of images

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship enabled me to support my work within the ISO/IEC SC29 WG1 related to standards development of JPEG. During this period, two activities on Quality Assessment Standardisation effort were in my focus, including:

- ▶ Objective quality assessment of Light Fields (ISO/IEC 21794-7 - JPEG Pleno Light Field Quality Assessment)
- ▶ Objective quality assessment of Image Coding (ISO/IEC 29170). A subdivision will be requested for the part 4.

Furthermore, I pursued my continuous participation in the JPEG Committee. The standards on Quality Evaluation are important for our TC because they establish models for the quality evaluation that can be used on the development of new editions of JPEG standards that target these modalities. They further establish quality evaluation models that can be adopted by developers in industry and academy, providing a general standardised quality evaluation model allowing direct comparison of the different solutions.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

JPEG currently is targeting two scenarios:

- ▶ Very High quality close to the visually lossless, JPEG AIC – 3 and JPEG AIC – 4: In recent years mechanisms for visualization of images/video improved to quality levels never experienced before. This created a grow on image quality and fidelity demand for what most of the existing quality models and quality evaluation standards were not designed for. To narrow the gap between the existing quality models and quality requests, the JPEG Committee started an investigation in new quality models that resulted in a call for contributions and the design of a new standard, called JPEG AIC – 3 Subjective quality assessment of high-fidelity images (ISO/IEC 29170-3). This standardisation effort was complemented with a call for proposals on Objective quality assessment of high-fidelity images, that is referred as JPEG AIC-4. A subdivision of the JPEG AIC standard will be requested, depending in the final evaluation of the call for proposals responses.

- ▶ JPEG Pleno Light Field Quality Assessment: JPEG Pleno development had led to the development of several quality models that were required for the evaluation of the multiple call for proposals, notably call for proposals on light field coding, call for evidence and call for proposals on point cloud coding and call for proposals on holography coding. This standardisation effort is built upon the knowledge acquired during the evaluation of the different responses to the JPEG Pleno call for proposals. It is the first standard addressing plenoptic content quality evaluation. Currently the current version of the Light Field Quality Evaluation (ISO/IEC 21794-7) is in DIS stage and is expected to become an international standard in the beginning of 2026. This standard will be extended with the final result produced after this call for proposals on Objective quality evaluation methodologies in a second edition.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The JPEG standardisation on quality evaluation will have strong impact in the definition of future JPEG standardized solutions, also these standards are instrumental for European SMEs in the field, like intoPIX. Also, JPEG is developing Standardised solutions with Prophese and Omnnivision.

In consequence, the development of this new standard is creating new business possibilities in the multimedia and its applications technological market based on the advances that result from the development. Notably, it is important to emphasise that the most active teams in the development of the JPEG standards are European groups that have been collaborating for its development.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. It is expected that the two calls will provide standardised objective quality assessment solutions after the evaluation. A process will be considered based on the evaluation of the proposals to pursue a standardised solution.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The successful response to the two calls target in this call, requires testing and evaluation that will be considered in the period between the 109th meeting and the 110th meeting that will be held in Sydney, Australia in January. My research group will participate in both evaluations.

Online references related to the fellowship work

<https://www.iso.org/committee/45316.html>

<https://jpeg.org/>

Extending and reinforcing commitments in Standardization for Robotics and AI for Healthcare

João Manuel Leitão Quintas

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Portugal*

Sector

Robotics and autonomous systems

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEEE SA P 1872.3 REMAR - Ontology for reasoning on multiple autonomous robots
IEEE SA P1872.2 Autonomous Robotics (AuR) Ontology Working Group
IEEE SA P1955 6GRobo - 6G Empowering Robotics

Role

Secretary of IEEE P1872.3

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship contributed to ongoing efforts related to standardization and European policy advising on topics related to mainly for Robotics and Autonomous Systems and Artificial Intelligence.

The key objective of this fellowship is to contribute to the discussions and creation of resources that can support and facilitate the dissemination and adoption of standards, policy and guidelines proposed by key opinion leaders involved mainly in the recently created Working Group that is developing the standard project IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots¹¹ and IEEE P1955 - Standard for 6G Empowering Robotics: Use Case Scenarios, Requirements, Architectural Impact, and Technical Assumptions¹².

In the current state of the art, the implementation of standard ontologies in Robotics and Autonomous Systems is still considered a challenge but is considered necessary. One of the main challenges faced by current working groups is still how to provide a unified way of representing the underlying semantics and defining the vocabulary to be used by the system, thereby allowing precise knowledge transfer for problem-solving and unambiguous communications between heterogeneous, autonomous systems.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

1. This fellowship supports my work in the discussions and creation of resources that can support and facilitate the dissemination and adoption of standards related to RAS & AI, mainly in the recently created Working Group developing the standard project IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots, where I accumulate the role of Secretary.
2. This activity supports my investment in dissemination and adoption of standards exploring

¹¹ <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1872.3/11037/>

¹² <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1955/11660/>

the potential of 6G technology in robotic applications, focusing on enhancing communication, real-time data processing, and cooperative behaviors among autonomous systems, mainly in the recently created Working Group IEEE P1955 - Standard for 6G Empowering Robotics: Use Case Scenarios, Requirements, Architectural Impact, and Technical Assumptions where I have the role of Member.

3. To support the continued efforts on promoting existing related standards like IEEE P1872.2 Standard for Autonomous Robotic (AUR) Ontology standard (standards.ieee.org/project/1872_2.html) and maintain the synergies with the experts currently involved in IEEE EPPC Working Group on ICT, where I served as a member in the biannual 2021-2022.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

SMEs related to robotics and/or developing artificial agents with a certain degree of autonomy can be impacted by this contribution, as the standard being developed aims to bring added value for integration and interoperability in solutions based on robotic and autonomous systems.

Impact on Society

This work is supporting the societal impact related to demographic change challenges. Solutions that may adhere to the standard should result in more interoperable, intelligent, sustainable and cost-effective technologies. Additionally, by leveraging the participation of EU experts in global outreach activities and the involvement in worldwide level initiatives contributes to position EU as a top player in the advances of ICT standardization.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

No, as my activity focused on disseminating already existing standards towards the target communities of users.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The landscape for standardization in Robotics account for near 100 applicable standards.

However, many are coming from other areas not specifically from autonomous and robotic (AuR) systems. Additionally, the overall standardization in terms of knowledge representations for AuR

are not sufficiently addressed, hence the motivation and need to continue creating new standardization projects (e.g. IEEE P1872.3). Moreover, in spite of the existing active standards we can still observe a lack of adoption. Possibly because some AuR applications did not become yet main stream, but this may be changing within the next 5 to 10 years, as other related fields evolve and societal challenges pressing demand for new technology-based solutions to be developed. Hence, it is my opinion that the state of maturity for the topic I am addressing is still in preliminary stage and requires a continuation of action.

Online references related to the fellowship work

<https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1872.3/11037>

<https://github.com/joaquintas/aurora>

Gap analysis, reference architecture and ontology for local digital twins

Torbjörn Lahrin

*Expert on Internet of Things, Digital Twins, CitiVerse, Metaverse and Smart Cities , Lahrin i Hajstorp AB
Sweden*

Sector

Smart and Sustainable Cities

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1 JWG with SyC Smart Cities on Urban Digital Twins and City Information Modelling

Role

Co-convenor JWG between JTC and SyC Smart Cities on Urban Digital Twins and City Information Modelling

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship addresses several gaps related to Local Digital twins (LTD). Local Digital Twins will be fundamental building blocks for CitiVerse. It will also play a crucial role for anyone in the public sector who wants to fully utilize the usage of AI. All comprehensive use of AI is depending on the supply of relevant underlying data. Today, cities, regions and countries all over the world are building Local Digital Twins using various tools and approaches. Game engines, CAD tools, GIS, AR/VR/XR tools, Urban Digital Platforms, CIM and other visualisation tools are used. Thus a wide spread of technologies and standards.

Interoperability for Local Digital Twins is crucial. They need to fit horizontally and vertically. Horizontally is to put a LDT of one city next to a LDT of another city and make them align. Vertically is that, by example, a LDT produced by a city must fit LDT from public transportation and LDT by the energy company for the same geographical area, etc.

Moreover, the European CitiVerse will be built upon Local Digital Twins. If separate Local Digital Twins in Europe doesn't fit together it will be impossible to create a seamless CitiVerse. It will also be difficult with interoperability between LDT:s. The LDT also needs interoperability versus dataspace and IoT. For a LDT:s to be useful for officials and others, LDT:s need interoperability with the business operating systems used by officials on daily basis.

With this regards, in the framework of this fellowship, I have supported conducting a survey to many major LDT project around the world, and we have now gathered the results and statistics. A first version of a gap analysis and Tech report as well as recommendations e to all relevant major SDOs on how to develop or change their standards to fit better together has been produced.

The JWG is also laying the foundation for producing an international reference architecture for LDT:s aligned with the international reference architectures for Digital Twins, IoT and Smart Cities among others. A NWIP for the proposes RA project has been produced, and we have created a first WD for the RA.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Local Digital Twins and CitiVerse involve many standards. The report “Landscape of CitiVerse Standards”, produced under StandICT.eu2026, where I was one of the co-authors, lists about 350 standards to be considered for LDT:s and CitiVerse. The JWG are analysing these and will give advice to major SDO:s dealing with these standards.

In this sense, my engagement contribute to European work regarding CitiVerse, since CitiVerse need to be built on Local Digital Twins. The upcoming reference architecture for Local Digital Twins will be

fundamental for CitiVerse.

Furthermore, the Terms of Reference for the JWG and project states that LDT reference architecture should be aligned with

- ▷ ISO/IEC 30141 - IoT Reference Architecture
- ▷ ISO/IEC 30188 – Digital Twin Reference Architecture
- ▷ IEC IEC 63205 – Smart Cities Reference Architecture.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society) Impact on Society

The work is laying the foundation for uniting the world in how to build Local Digital Twins (Urban Digital Twins and City Information Modelling) and how to make these interoperable with each other both horizontal, vertical and towards underlying data sets and daily operation systems of cities and other authorities. It is also paving the road for how Local Digital Twins can be used as the foundation for building CitiVerse.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

The JWG and project is expected to give guidance to all SDO:s having standard related to Local Digital Twins and CityVerse. Furthermore, my JWG has been assigned the task to create an international ISO/IEC reference architecture for Local Digital Twins in alignment with ISO/IEC 30188, ISO/IEC 30141, IEC 63205 – Smart Cities Reference Architecture and other relevant standards.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The work is still ongoing and will continue for at least over a year more. The first version of the gap

analysis is provided to National Bodies for commenting and will be finalized during Autumn 2025. From this gap analysis, we will extract stakeholders and their concerns (needs). This will be the foundation for developing the Local Digital Twin Reference Architecture. It will also serve as a foundation for producing a Local Digital Twin Ontology.

The work spans over several years and is carried out in accordance with the plans and decisions by JTC1 and SyC Smart Cities. However, the work will be highly relevant for the ned JTC4 - Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:14:404930262863078:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:49078,25

■ Lifts and Escalators in Smart Cities

Gero Gschwendtner

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Sector

Smart and Sustainable Cities

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 178 Lifts, escalators and moving walks
ISO/TC 178/ WG 4 Safety requirements and risk assessment
ISO/TC 178/ WG 5 Escalators and moving walks
ISO/TC 178/ WG 6 Lift installation
CEN/TC 10 Lifts, escalators and moving walks
CEN/TC 10/WG 2 Escalators and moving walks
Joint Working Group (JWG) CEN/ TC 10 + SESA + SAC/ TC 196 +
ON AG 017 Aufzüge und Fahrtreppen
ON AG 017.02 Fahrtreppen und Fahrsteige
Global Technical Advisory Group of WEEF (World Elevator and
Escalator Federation)

Role

Chairman ISO/TC 178 Lifts, Escalator and Moving Walks

Convenor CEN/TC 10/WG 2 Escalator and Moving Walks

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Until 2022, the lift and escalator sector lacked dedicated ICT standards beyond the initial cybersecurity framework (ISO 8102 20). Traditionally, the sector embedded emerging topics within the core product standards — ISO 8100 1/2 and EN 115 1 — often referred to as the “product bibles.” However, with increasing complexity and rapid technological change, it became clear that this approach could no longer accommodate the specific demands of ICT integration.

To address this, ISO/TC 178 initiated a strategic shift: identifying ICT as a key gap and launching targeted standardization projects. These include not only cybersecurity but also remote software updates (ISO/TS 8102 21), access control and monitoring systems (ISO/TS 8100 10/11), BIM integration, interoperability, and more. These developments are now treated as standalone priorities while still interfacing with the core product standards — which themselves must be continuously updated to reflect relevant general ICT aspects.

A parallel challenge is geopolitical: the accelerated pace of national standardization in China, often bypassing international processes. China's rapid development of local ICT-related lift standards poses a risk of fragmentation. Therefore, strategic engagement with SAC has intensified — including bilateral working groups and regular technical exchanges — to ensure alignment, avoid duplication, and encourage adoption of ISO standards at the national level.

In summary, the key gaps addressed are the historical absence of ICT-specific standards, the need to prioritize modular but coordinated standardization efforts, and the global challenge of maintaining coherence amid divergent regulatory speeds.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Lifts, escalators, and moving walks are critical to ensuring safe, accessible, and energy-efficient mobility within buildings. While safety and accessibility have long been core priorities, the integration of ICT has become increasingly essential for enabling smart functionality, system resilience, and digital interoperability.

ISO/TC 178 has positioned ICT at the heart of its current standardization agenda. The dedicated Working Group 12 “Cybersecurity” was established in 2019 and successfully published ISO 8102 20 Cybersecurity. To align with new EU regulatory frameworks, a revision of this standard has now been launched where this project moved to stage 50.20 since 09.09.2025 with FDIS ballot preparation initiated.

Additionally WG 12 is progressing ISO/TS 8102 21 On-site and Off-site Software Updates, addressing a key gap in lifecycle digital security and functionality. This project moved to stage 50.20 since 09.09.2025 where FDIS ballot preparation is now initiated.

In parallel, WG 13 “New Technologies” was established at the end of 2022. It is leading the development of ISO/TS 8100 10 Building Information Modelling (BIM), which moved to stage 60.00 with FDIS closed on 21.10.2025 and publication process is now initiated. In addition ISO/TS 8100 11 Interoperability between lifts and other systems, is now through NP ballot stage and the CD draft is planned for end of this year. These projects are vital for integration into smart building environments.

All ICT-related standards are closely aligned with the ongoing work on the core product standards — ISO 8100 1, ISO 8100 2, ISO 8103 1 as well as the risk management and energy standards (ISO 14798 1, ISO TR 14798 2, ISO 25745-2). These serve as implementation frameworks, ensuring ICT requirements are embedded into real-world systems.

Through this coordinated approach, the funded application contributes directly to a future-proof, secure, and interoperable ICT standardization landscape for vertical mobility systems.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

ISO/TC 178 actively engages with European SMEs through formal liaisons with the European Lift Association (ELA) and SBS–Small Business Standards, where EFESME represents SME interests. Both organizations participate directly in ISO/TC 178 and working group meetings, especially on ICT-related topics.

As Chair, I ensure their input is given sufficient time and weight, allowing SMEs to raise concerns and contribute to shaping standards — even when this means balancing strong positions from larger companies. This inclusive governance ensures that standards reflect the realities of both major manufacturers and smaller industry players.

Impact on Society

Lifts, escalators, and moving walks are vital for ensuring safe and efficient access to buildings. Globally, there are over 18 million lifts and escalators in operation, with nearly half located in Europe. Each year, more than 1 million new units are installed. Approximately 325 million passengers use lifts daily, while escalators and moving walks support over 10 billion rides every day.

In the coming decades, the population aged 65 and above is projected to grow by nearly 33%, with those over 80 doubling in number. As the global population ages, accessibility becomes increasingly critical. Multi-floor buildings will require vertical transportation systems, including lifts, escalators, stair lifts, and platform lifts, to accommodate the growing demand for accessible infrastructure.

As essential components of building functionality, lifts, escalators, and moving walks are classified as modes of transport. They ensure safe access for all and are designed for free and independent use by passengers. This underscores the importance of robust safety measures to protect users.

By establishing harmonized safety and performance standards, these efforts support the

development of resilient, accessible, and low-impact urban environments that are better prepared for demographic and environmental change.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, in the framework of this fellowship, I contributed notably to the development of the following standards:

- ▶ ISO/TS 8100-10 Part 10: Building Information Modelling
- ▶ ISO/TS 8102-21 Part 21: Software updates
- ▶ ISO/TS 8100-11 Part 11: Interoperability between lift and other systems
- ▶ ISO/TS 8100-12 Part 11: System related operational conditions for remote functions

In addition, for the following standards a revision was initiated:

- ▶ ISO/TS 8102-20 Part 20: Cybersecurity
- ▶ ISO 25745-2 Energy performance of lifts, escalators and moving walks — Part 2: Energy calculation and classification for lifts (elevators)

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

As agreed by all ISO/TC 178 stakeholders, ICT standards play a pivotal role in shaping the future of the lift and escalator industry. Numerous ICT-related standardisation initiatives are currently in progress, and it remains crucial to see these projects through to successful completion and publication. At the same time, sustained advancement across all other ISO/TC 178 standardization activities is vital. In particular, the implementation of ICT standards must be effectively complemented and strengthened by the wider portfolio of interrelated standards under development.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/53970.html

 <https://elevatorworld.com/de/Artikel/ISO-Plenarsitzung/>

Concluding standardisation of AI enabled Photovoltaics (AIPV) under the StandICT support

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Sector

Smart Grids and Smart Metering

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

EITCI SMART-PV-SESG (Smart Energy Standards Group)
CENELEC / IEC-TC CLC/TC-82 Solar photovoltaic energy systems)
CLC/TC-57 Power systems management and associated information exchange

Role

Chair of the EITCI Smart Energy Standards Group (SESG)

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

A major gap identified in the current AI standardisation effort is lack of standards for directly applying AI to smart PV systems. The ICT standards role in energy, primarily focusing on smart grid management, grid-balancing and device interfacing is crucial. Rapidly growing smart PV market is witnessing significant AI-based innovations in solar cells from various vendors that would benefit from further standardisation. Continued efforts in this scope are important to support the EU Rolling Plan 2025 for ICT standardisation¹³ in line with EU policies on Smart Grids and Smart Metering. A key focus is further development of AI-enabled smart PV solar systems. This work aims to provide support for reference standardisation of identified primary domains of AI applications in PV systems. These include AI-assisted optimization of solar cell designs and production phases, planning of optimal solar cell system deployments, and optimization of solar cell operation within smart power grid systems.

Specific AI smart PV applications that need further conceptual and technical reference standards fall into three main areas: material discovery and optimization approaches (e.g. novel structures for the 3rd-generation solar cells and AI methods for optimizing modeling of PV devices during design and production phases), layout and deployment optimization (e.g. applying AI in weather forecasting, insolation analytics for irradiation mapping, and other factors influencing smart PV deployments), efficiency optimization and integration with smart grids (fault detection, energy forecasting, lifecycle assessment, and decommissioning process optimization, this includes applying AI for carbon intensity awareness, integrating AI with smart meter data to enhance Smart Grid awareness, performance loss rate determination, power and net-load forecasting, behind-the-meter PV visibility, intelligent hybrid/smart inverters, and AI methods for Maximum Power Point Tracking, MPPT).

¹³ <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/smart-grids-and-smart-metering-rp2025>

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The action contributes to advancing reference standards by combining progress in AI with renewable energy generated in grid-connected photovoltaic (PV) systems, along with their smart design and production on the devices level, deployment optimization, operation-and-maintenance and smart on-grid integration and control. Continued standardisation efforts in AI-assisted smart PV are expected to expand the digital energy standards inventory and support the adoption of crucial smart energy technologies aligned with the EU climate and energy policy framework. This is particularly relevant given the emphasis on integrating digital and green agendas as key pillars of the EU development strategy. The standardisation efforts aim to define a higher level of abstraction for potential AI applications in smart PV systems across all scales, from residential installations to PV power plants. The goal is to develop SESG published technical reference documents for AI assisted smart PV and ensure integration with other established standards for smart energy and smart grids.

This fellowship supports my efforts as the coordinator of the Smart PV workgroup of the EITCI SESG, established in 2019. This cross-SDO WG includes members contributing to relevant smart energy WGs of international SDOs/SSOs, promoting cooperation in drafting and disseminating smart PV standards for the future. SESG has grown impressively from 30 members in 2020 to over 170 members in 2025. The action coordinator invited IEC contributors from the Committee 8B/77/CD, as well as of S2 standard, former EFI (with FAN), and the SMEST2. Contributions to EITCI SMART-PV-SESG may extend to CEN/CENELEC, IEC-TC CLC/TC-82 (Solar photovoltaic energy systems), and CLC/TC-57 (Power systems management and associated information exchange) for power systems control equipment and systems, including EMS (Energy Management Systems) and SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition).

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The smart energy is currently not only an important market trend of a dynamic growth and rapid technological development, but also a central axis in the EU's Green Deal strategy joining ICT and energy sectors as main pillars for the EU development facing serious energy challenges. Furthermore, the green transformation is currently considered to be an important aspect of the European energy security, especially in view of the international situation, the Russian invasion on Ukraine and the threat of an energy crisis concerning the hydrocarbons. In regard to these challenges the European Commission plans to secure advancing renewable energy technologies further enabled by ICT and ensure a leading global position of the EU in smart energy, transforming the global warming and international situation challenges into a growth opportunity for EU SMEs driving European innovation with a focus on smart energy. Hence the project implemented international standardisation efforts support EU SMEs.

Impact on Society

AI assisted smart PV systems enhance efficiency and performance of solar energy. By optimizing design, production, deployment and operation of PV, AI can maximize energy generation, leading to increased renewable energy adoption, reducing reliance on fossil fuels. This is especially important in the context of the challenging international situation, as well as helps mitigate the environmental impact of energy production and addressing the problem of the related climate change.

Standardisation driven adoption of AI enabled smart PV technology supports transition to a cleaner and more sustainable energy future globally. AI enabled smart PV systems can greatly enhance resilience of the energy infrastructure in general. By generating electricity in an optimized way closer to the point of consumption, they reduce vulnerability to power outages and disruptions. Moreover, in remote or off-grid areas, smart PV technology can provide reliable and decentralized energy solutions, promoting energy independence and access to electricity. Finally the dynamic market uptake of AI enabled smart PV technology supported by standardisation efforts will generate demand for new, skilled professionals in

areas joining competences in PV and AI/ML. This creates employment opportunities and contributes to society economic growth. Additionally, the growth of the renewable energy sector can stimulate private investments and foster innovation, leading to new business ventures and entrepreneurship.

Discussion on the AI assisted smart PV standards social impacts took place on the 2022 SET (Strategic Energy Technology) Plan Conference where I was invited as a speaker by the European Commission¹⁴. The European Commission's SET Plan Conference is a major European energy policy event, shaping the EU's energy future.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

The action led to further development and publication of advanced versions of the technical reference standards of the EITCI SESG with economic modeling inclusions: 1) AIPV systems definitions, concepts, architectures and use cases, and 2) AIPV technical specification of processes and devices.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The current extensions in Smart PV reference standards included following specifications areas:

- ▶ Solar cell devices design and production phase
- ▶ Planning of optimal PV systems deployments
- ▶ Optimization of solar modules operation in power systems (with a focus on AI integrated Smart PV modules)

All items include an economic cost-optimization modeling framework as investing in smart PV requires cost-effectiveness and optimal performance. AI-enabled cost-optimization modeling enhances decision-making by analyzing complex variables across multiple domains and levels, integrating AI methods for cost optimization and investment scopes definition in regard to devices and their efficiencies and external costs in providing needed economic recommendations.

These economic modeling inclusions extending the previously solely technical referencing are however on a preliminary level and still require a continuation of the action. Collaborative approach in further Smart PV standardization will help to solidify the role of AI in transforming solar energy to a more reliable and economically feasible power source globally

Online references related to the fellowship work

<https://eitci.org/technology-certification/sesg>

<https://eitci.org/smart-energy-standards-group.pdf>

<https://eitci.org/technology-certification/sesg/smart-pv>

<https://eitci.org/technology-certification/sesg/smart-pv/eitci-sesg-smart-pv-concepts>

<https://eitci.org/technology-certification/sesg/smart-pv/eitci-sesg-smart-pv-technical>

14 <https://www.setplan2022.eu/speakers>

5. Societal challenges

Participation in the ISO/TC215 Health Informatics meetings in Toronto October 2025

Alpo Värri

*Research Director in the Faculty of Medicine and Health Technology, Tampere University
Finland*

Sector

Digital health, healthy living and ageing

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 215 Health informatics

ISO/TC 215/CAG 1 Executive council, harmonization and operations

ISO/TC 215/TF 5 AI technologies in health informatics

ISO/TC 215/WG 2 Systems and Device Interoperability

ISO/TC 215/WG 11 Personalized digital health

ISO/TC 215/JWG 7 Joint ISO/TC 215 - IEC/SC 62A WG: Safe, effective and secure health software and health IT systems, including those incorporating medical devices

CEN/TC251 Health Informatics WG2 Technology and applications

Role

Convener of CEN/TC251 Health Informatics WG2 Technology and applications

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

CEN/TC251 Health Informatics is a standards delivery organisation, meaning that it approves standards in Europe, but the standards do not have to be created in Europe. In fact, many of them come from the global health informatics committee ISO/TC215. For this reason, it is important to monitor and contribute to the standards prepared in ISO/TC215. This is what the purpose of this fellowship was about.

ISO/TC215 has around 10 working groups (WGs) and CEN/TC251 has two. I am the convener of the second one and I try to follow those ISO/TC215 WGs that operate within the scope of my WG in CEN/TC251. This is not always easy because the ISO/TC215 WG meetings take place at the same time. In ISO/TC215 I participate mainly in interoperability, information security, and health software development areas.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is coming to healthcare, too. As I have AI experience through my doctoral studies and projects that followed, it has been natural for me to follow AI standardisation, too. The ISO/TC215 meeting in Toronto in October 2025 made it clear that the number of AI related work items is increasing in ISO/TC215. ISO/TC215 has a joint working group 3 (JWG3) with JTC1/SC42 Artificial Intelligence. The idea is that the ISO/TC215 AI work items are developed in this JWG3. Attendance in JWG3 is important also because I am a member of the CEN Strategic Advisory Group on AI in healthcare.

During the ISO/TC215 Toronto meetings in October 2025, SC42 held its meetings in Sydney, Australia. After the working day was over in Toronto, work began in Sydney in Toronto evening time. I participated in particularly the healthcare AI standards development JWG3 and SC42/

WG4 Use Cases meetings virtually in Sydney. Attendance in JWG3 meetings was important to motivate the ISO/TC215 initiated standardisation projects to the SC42 leadership. Through my participation, the other parties became more aware of European values in AI standardisation.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This one shot fellowship supported my participation to a physical ISO meeting in Canada, in October 2025.

This participation is crucial: as the drafting of standards lasts typically years and one meeting can contribute to their completion in a limited, but often very useful way. Face-to-face meetings and coffee break discussions build trust and understanding among the experts, which contributes the consensus building in standards development. I noticed a clear difference during the COVID-19 virtual-only meeting period when new projects started with new experts to each other. There was some observable micromanagement when the experts had not built the trust in face-to-face meetings.

During the Toronto meetings, I was among those approving the next steps of a number of standard projects that had made good progress between the meetings. In addition to those I contributed particularly to the development of the following standards:

- ▷ ISO/WD TS 24292 Health informatics - Dental Data for Exchange
- ▷ ISO/CD 24973 Health informatics - Digital therapeutics - Product requirements
- ▷ IEC/AWI 81001-5-1 Health software and health IT systems safety, effectiveness and security - Part 5-1: Security - Activities in the product life cycle
- ▷ ISO/AWI 81001-5-2 Health software and health IT systems safety, effectiveness and security - Part 5-2: Security Risk Management for Manufacturers

Some new work items do not have a name and a number yet. One important example of these is the document about AI management for healthcare based on the horizontal SC42 standard ISO/IEC 42001:2023 Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Management system.

In addition, ISO/TC215/CAG1 consists of the heads of delegation of the P members in TC215. CAG1 was asked for input to the new business plan of ISO/TC215. My contribution has been to suggest that standards that support the implementation of the European Health Data Space regulation and the Data Act are to be prepared in ISO/TC215.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Due to my background in the university, I look for opportunities to commercialise the results of our research projects in a start-up company. When I have this approach in my mind, I try to contribute to the standards in such a way that their implementation does not require a large organisation. For example, this week I commented in a AI Risk Management System standard comment resolution meeting that this form of requirements means that the company has to have at least four people to be able to comply with the standard.

Impact on Society

Information technology supports the delivery of healthcare, making it safer, more effective and patient-friendly by making the personal health information accessible to the patients themselves. The standardisation work in ISO/TC215 supports these developments.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute consciously to the development of new ISO standards on Health informatics, as described here above.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I am not working on only one standard but many of them. They are in various stages of maturity. The ones with are coming to a second version are typically quite mature, but some of the new ones may be partly immature and implementation attempts will tell what needs to be updated.

There are projects where experts with knowledge about European regulations are needed, but in some cases, this is not equally important. So, it depends case by case on the closeness of European regulations to the scope of the standard.

Online references related to the fellowship work

📄 CEN/TC251 in Europe: <https://www.ehealth-standards.eu>

📄 ISO/TC215 Health Informatics committee: <https://www.iso.org/committee/54960.html>

Towards standardisation of air quality sensor systems

Sergi Udina

*Senior Researcher and sensors expert, Bettair Cities
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Sector

Digital health, healthy living and ageing

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN TC/264 Air Quality WG41 Emissions and ambient air -
Instrumental odour monitoring
CEN TC/264 WG42 Ambient air - Air quality sensors

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The implementation of the European air quality directive requires development of related technical guidelines and harmonisation, CEN/TC264/WG42 addresses that, so far with the issue of TS17660-1 and TS17660-2 (available since Dec 24).

In particular, after issuing a technical specification for the measurement of toxic gases and particulate matter, WG42 is looking into QA/QC practices (a main market concern) and mobile air quality sensors (in increasing demand).

These relate to the need of ensuring the continued reliable and accurate operation of sensor systems to measure air quality.

In addition, European citizens see their right to breathe clean air and to be free from unpleasant odours are compromised by a lack of regulation and technical resources to determine liability and to faithfully establish a situation of violation. CEN/TC264/WG41 addresses that situation to help industries determine their olfactory impacts using sound and reliable technical methods, and thus allow a clear regulatory framework to be established.

In general, the topic of air quality measurements using sensors lacks mechanisms to offer trust to users, industries, and institutions. Both CEN/TC264/WG41 and WG42 address that for two slightly different problems: air pollution and odorous nuisances.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship supports my work in the two CEN TCG 264 WGs.

CEN/TC264/WG42 has issued the technical specifications TS17660-1 and TS17660-2, the latter published this last December 2024, WG42 is currently drafting a Technical Report dealing with QA/QC protocols.

Regarding CEN/TC264/WG41, we are finalizing the first draft of the three documents that will be submitted to TC264 for publication as a Technical Specification at first, and then a Standard. Publication is expected in 2026.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

There are many European SMEs trying to tackle the challenge of air quality in different ways and environments. In general, SMEs have a harder time generating trust than large companies due to fewer resources in communication, the availability of reliable protocols, metrics and institutions to establish the quality of sensor systems is paramount to aid SMEs in building trust in their products. The trust wheel starts spinning with good protocols and standards, and this is what this work aims to do in both aspects for air pollutants and olfactory nuisances.

Impact on Society

These targeted standards enable improved evidence-based policy making by ensuring sensor data reliability. Environmental awareness as a motor for environmental behaviour change by making air quality measurements affordable to a larger community. At a large scale, healthier living in cities by improving the common awareness of the air quality of cities and possible mitigation actions.

Also, these standards prone more sustainable industrial activity by improving the knowledge about generated pollution and odour nuisances. On the other hand improved data availability for scientific models, early warning and forecasting, contribute to larger availability with lower cost systems, with sufficient data quality and accuracy.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, especially the preparatory work within CEN TC 264/WG42 is now facing proposal to conversion to a standard.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Regarding CEN/TC264/WG42 an elaboration of part 3 covering QA/QC practices is ongoing and now in draft revision stage. This part is important since it tackles the very relevant issue of data reliability along the lifetime of sensor systems.

Regarding CEN/TC264/WG41 a first draft proposal is conceptually finalised and under revision of writing before submission in the coming days. In this sense work towards the draft is almost finalised but it is expected to face some revisions after feedback from TC264.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/ords/f?p=205:7::::FSP_ORG_ID:6245&cs=1BE3755617138EC4BB13ACDB8E1AC7A17

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